

Master's Thesis

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Microbial fermentation of faba beans:

Characterization of key microorganisms, their interactions and effects on functional properties

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Abstract

Faba beans (*Vicia faba*), like other legumes, are a promising sustainable protein source. However, faba beans contain antinutritional factors and off-flavor compounds, limiting broad consumer acceptance. Microbial fermentation shows promise as a sustainable alternative to conventional methods for mitigating these compounds. Consequently, a deeper understanding of fermentation-relevant microorganisms and their potential to improve faba bean quality is needed. Therefore, this master's thesis evaluated *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* 2-1, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *Bacillus subtilis* var. *natto* in liquid and solid-state fermentation of faba beans. Deploying both mono- and co-cultures, it was revealed that all strains exhibited growth, with some strains distinctly affecting pH across both fermentation systems. The only exception was *Bacillus subtilis* var. *natto*, which was not detectable during liquid co-culture fermentation with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13. Additionally, a spot agar assay revealed inhibitory interactions, with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 and *L. plantarum* 2-1 inhibiting *B. subtilis* var. *natto* and each other. Similar effects were observed among additional strains of the two LAB species. A trypsin inhibitor assay revealed that samples from solid-state fermentation containing *B. subtilis* var. *natto* significantly decreased trypsin inhibitor activity. Moreover, GC-MS analysis showed that solid-state fermentation with all strains substantially changed the VOC profile of faba beans, including reductions in concentrations of certain “beany” off-flavor aldehydes such as hexanal. Lastly, a confocal microscopy methodology was tested out to examine structural changes in faba beans, which, with method optimization, might be promising. Overall, the results obtained during this thesis help further the understanding of microbial fermentation of faba beans and provide a foundation upon which future work can build.

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1. Introduction

As the environmental, climate, and nutritional consequences of animal-based food production become more evident, a global demand for sustainable protein sources continues to increase. Consequently, plant-based protein sources are being highlighted as sustainable alternatives to animal-based protein, as their production emits lower amounts of greenhouse gases while also requiring significantly less land and water (Lumsden et al., 2024).

1.1 Legumes

A promising source of plant-based protein comes in the form of legumes. These plants, belonging to the taxonomic family *Fabaceae*, commonly known as legumes, have a rich historical and agricultural role in serving as either an important food source for humans or as a protein-rich feed in animal production (Crépon et al., 2010). Furthermore, the extensive cultivation history and notable diversity within the *Fabaceae* family have resulted in a large variety of legumes being available for human consumption. Commonly, for legumes, humans consume the seeds, in which the major component is the internal storage tissue known as the cotyledon, which is surrounded by the seed coat or testa (Figure 1) (Bohra et al., 2022; Sharan et al., 2020). This tissue provides the basis for why the nutritional profile of legumes is so appealing, as it hosts an array of nutrients essential for germination, including, most importantly, protein (Sharan et al., 2020).

Figure 1: Illustration of a *V. faba* seed (left) highlighting cotyledon (C), testa (T), embryonic shoot (P), and the embryonic root (R). (right) illustration of the structure within the cotyledon, highlighting the cell wall (CW), starch granules (S), and protein bodies (PB) (Sharan et al., 2020)

The composition of the cotyledon is made up of different components. Firstly, legume seeds possess an impressive amount of protein, which makes them a great source when it comes to fulfilling human protein intake. The majority of the protein content found is seed storage proteins, which are in the form of protein bodies (Figure 1, PB) (Sharan et al., 2020). These seed storage proteins are critical to the plant because they provide the necessary nutrients during seed germination, respiratory metabolism, and seedling establishment. Moreover, they are also essential in the regulation of metabolic processes and physiological and biochemical processes (Y. Liu et al., 2017).

Legumes are also a great source of carbohydrates, primarily in the form of starch, an insoluble carbohydrate made up of amylose and amylopectin. Starch makes up a significant portion of the legume seeds and is located in starch granules (Figure 1, S) that surround the protein bodies in the cotyledon. These larger structures act as carbohydrate storage/energy reserves that are dormant until germination, where a supply of energy/carbon is needed (Pfister & Zeeman, 2016; Sharan et al., 2020; Tayade et al., 2019).

1.1.2 *Vicia faba*

The legume this project revolves around is *Vicia faba*, commonly known as faba bean. As a member of the *Fabaceae* family, its seeds possess the above-mentioned qualities, making it a promising candidate as a plant-based protein source with a strong nutritional profile, containing high levels of protein, dietary fiber, and other relevant bioactive compounds (Sharan et al., 2020). Moreover, the faba bean also harbours other advantageous qualities, such as having an impressive protein-carbohydrate ratio, the ability to be cultivated in the European climate, and its beneficial symbiotic relationship with soil bacteria. This relationship enables nitrogen fixation, elevation of organic matter concentration, and solubilization of phosphorus (Mayer Labba et al., 2021).

Despite the advantageous attributes associated with faba beans and legumes in general, their consumption faces different kinds of challenges related to compounds found naturally within legumes, two of the main ones being antinutrients and a challenging aroma profile plagued by off-flavors. (Mayer Labba et al., 2021; Ritter et al., 2024).

1.2 Antinutrients

Antinutrients are compounds that reduce the digestibility and absorption of the nutrients contained within the consumed plant product and are therefore viewed as undesirable, as they negatively impact human health (Mayer Labba et al., 2021). Within faba beans, several antinutrients are found, such as lectin, trypsin inhibitors, saponins, phytate, vicine, and convicine (Mayer Labba et al., 2021). These compounds serve a key biological role for the plant, often centred around protecting the plant from herbivores, insects, and diseases (Salim et al., 2023).

Saponins exemplify this by naturally protecting legumes against infections caused by herbivory and microbes, but when consumed in large concentrations by humans, saponins can cause alterations in the integrity of intestinal epithelial cells and change the intestinal epithelial layer permeability, resulting in leakage (Nath et al., 2022).

Another example is the naturally occurring phosphorus compound phytate, which is the basis of phytic acid and is commonly found in legumes. Its primary role is the storage of phosphate for the plant, making up approximately 75% of the phosphate content found in seeds, mainly located in the protein bodies of the cotyledon (Figure 1), functioning as an energy source and antioxidant during germination (Buades Fuster et al., 2017; Petroski & Minich, 2020). However, when consumed by humans, phytic acid can reduce the absorption and digestion rate of key nutritional elements as the compound reacts, binds, and forms insoluble complexes with polyvalent cations like magnesium, zinc, calcium, and iron, all of which are essential minerals that are important nutrients in the human diet (Buades Fuster et al., 2017).

A third commonly found antinutrient in legumes is trypsin inhibitors, which is the class of antinutrients this project will focus on.

1.2.1 Trypsin inhibitors

Trypsin inhibitors, like other antinutrients, are metabolites naturally found within legumes, and their primary function revolves around protection against pest attacks. The location within the seed of these metabolites differs depending on the legume type, with > 90% of trypsin inhibitors being localized in the cotyledon for faba beans (Figure 1). Furthermore, the

concentration of trypsin inhibitors also varies across legume types, with *Glycine max* (soybean) bolstering a higher concentration than faba beans (Avilés-Gaxiola et al., 2018).

Trypsin inhibitors are proteins found in legumes that get their antinutritional qualities from inhibiting the digestive enzymes trypsin and chymotrypsin. These enzymes are produced by the pancreas in animals and serve a key role in the digestion process of dietary protein. After intake of protein and initial digestion in the mouth and stomach, where the low pH activates pepsinogen into pepsin, resulting in the cleavage of peptide bonds, the remaining components travel to the duodenum. Here, the proenzymes trypsinogen and chymotrypsinogen are present, having been delivered by the pancreas. Mucosal enterokinase, a key digestion enzyme produced by cells in the duodenum, initiates the proenzymes and their conversion into trypsin and chymotrypsin. These two enzymes differ in their respective cleavage sites, as trypsin cleaves at basic amino acids while chymotrypsin cleaves aromatic amino acids, allowing for a more comprehensive breakdown into amino acids, dipeptides, and tripeptides. This key digestion process and the two aforementioned enzymes are, however, impaired by trypsin inhibitors, as the inhibitors form indigestible complexes with the digestion enzymes (Avilés-Gaxiola et al., 2018; Kiela & Ghishan, 2016; Loblely et al., 1977).

In legumes, trypsin inhibitors are classified into two main groups depending on their molecular size. Both classes are found in soybeans, which is not the case for all legumes, and investigations regarding their structure and inactivation methods have predominantly been conducted in soybeans, resulting in the most thorough descriptions and the highest number of studies. Therefore, soybeans act as a representative model for describing the chemical structures and properties (Avilés-Gaxiola et al., 2018; Luo et al., 2025).

Firstly, the larger Kunitz trypsin inhibitors (≈ 20 kDa), which are 170 to 200 amino acids long, globulin-type, non-glycosylated monomeric proteins. Moreover, these proteins also contain two disulfide bonds (Figure 2), and the protein structure is stabilized through hydrogen bonds connecting antiparallel β -strands. The inhibition of trypsin occurs through the protein's active sites, which are located at amino acid residues arginine 63 and isoleucine 64, where the protein reacts with trypsin, resulting in inactivation (Figure 2) (Avilés-Gaxiola et al., 2018; Luo et al., 2025).

Secondly, there are the Bowman-Birk trypsin inhibitors (≈ 8 kDa), which in soybeans are 71 amino acids long proteins held together by the cross-linking of seven disulfide bonds. In contrast to the Kunitz trypsin inhibitors, the Bowman-Birk trypsin inhibitors contain two independent active sites. One of them is at lysine 16-serine 17 (Figure 2), where inhibition of trypsin occurs through a hydrogen bond between the N-terminal domain of lysine 16 and aspartic acid 189 located in trypsin, resulting in inactivation of trypsin's catalytic site. The second site is responsible for the inhibition of chymotrypsin, which occurs through the binding of the hydrophobic side chain of leucine 43 and the hydrophobic pocket found in chymotrypsin, ultimately resulting in the inhibition of the enzyme (Avilés-Gaxiola et al., 2018; Luo et al., 2025)

Figure 2: Structural overview of the two trypsin inhibitor types: Kunitz trypsin inhibitors (KTI) and Bowman-Birk inhibitor (BBI) (from soybean). KTI: Upper part highlights the disulfide bond, whereas the lower part highlights the active site at Arg 63 and Ile 64. BBI: The two highlighted parts illustrate the two independent inhibition sites against trypsin and chymotrypsin, respectively (Luo et al., 2025).

As trypsin inhibitors are undesirable compounds, many traditional methods have been effectively deployed with the aim of reducing their presence/activity in legumes. For example, it has been shown that applying thermal treatment in the form of cooking pre-soaked faba beans at 95 °C for 1 hour can reduce the trypsin and chymotrypsin inhibitory activity by 100% (Shi et al., 2017). Furthermore, it has also been shown that extrusion can significantly reduce the trypsin inhibitor level in faba beans (with preconditioning) (Adamidou et al., 2011).

1.3 Volatile organic compounds and off-flavor

One of the main obstacles for plant protein products, and especially legumes, is the high content of undesirable aroma compounds, hindering acceptance by consumers. These compounds contribute to a sensory profile plagued by rancid and especially “beany” off-flavors (Leonard et al., 2023). While flavor is dependent on a multitude of factors like taste, aroma, and mouthfeel, this project will focus on volatile organic compounds (VOCs) (Queiroz et al., 2024)

VOCs in plants are small molecules emitted in response to environmental stressors, which can be either biotic factors like pest attacks, diseases, and parasites, or abiotic factors like drought, heat, or poor soil conditions. In response to said factors, the plant uses VOCs as defence mechanisms, which, with their low molecular weight and high vapor pressure, are able to effectively evaporate, allowing the compounds to quickly reach their intended targets. In addition, VOCs found in plants showcase incredible diversity across a vast array of chemical classes, such as aldehydes, alcohols, ketones, and pyrazines. Moreover, VOCs are not exclusively located within one part of the plant, as emissions and presence are found in flowers, leaves, and fruits, which consequently means the consumed seeds from legumes also contain VOCs. This incredible diversity represents the plants’ capabilities of interacting with and in response to an ever-changing environment (Avesani et al., 2025; Fischer et al., 2022).

1.3.1 “Beany” off-flavor compounds

A key example of how certain VOCs impact the aroma profile is the compounds contributing to the “beany” off-flavor found in legumes. This off-flavor stems from a multitude of different VOCs and combinations of these. Moreover, these compounds can be intrinsically found within the legume or formed due to storage or processing (Kaur et al., 2025). The pathways leading to the formation of these volatiles can be divided into two main categories, with the first being lipid oxidation (Fischer et al., 2022).

The production of different volatiles during lipid oxidation is diverse since the substrate is not fixed. Different fatty acids can undergo oxidation, like linoleic acid, linolenic acid, and oleic acid, resulting in different pathways. These oxidation pathways can either be enzymatic or non-enzymatic if oxygen is present (autooxidation). The enzymatic path involves the enzyme lipoxygenase (LOX), which oxidizes free acids released from the reaction between lipase and

triglycerides. This oxidation causes the conversion into fatty acid hydroperoxides (HPOD), which, when broken down by hydroperoxide lyase (HPL), results in the formation of a volatile compound and an oxo-acid. Further transformation of these compounds can occur, resulting in compounds that can undergo conversion into different alcohols. This conversion occurs through the enzyme alcohol dehydrogenase (ADH), which is thought to be integral to the conversion of “beany” off-flavor compounds, as it can convert aldehydes into less odorant primary alcohols. (Fischer, Cayot and Cachon, 2022). A key example of this is the major volatile compound hexanal, which formed as a result of lipid oxidation. Hexanal is an aldehyde considered to be one of the greatest and most influential compounds concerning the “beany” off-flavor with a 4.5 ppb threshold (Bott & Chambers IV, 2006; Fischer et al., 2022). The aldehyde is primarily formed during linoleic acid oxidation, but can also occur during the oxidation of linolenic acid. Hexanal can then be further converted by ADH to hexanol, which has a lower threshold of 0.09-5.2 ppb (Fischer et al., 2022; Hashem et al., 2022) (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Formation of hexanal during lipid oxidation from linoleic acid (upper) and linolenic acid (lower). Auto: autoxidation. ADH: alcohol dehydrogenase. Modified from (Fischer et al., 2022).

The second pathway leading to the formation of aroma compounds is the degradation of amino acids, products released as a result of proteolysis. An example of such compounds could be the nitrogen-containing pyrazines. Additionally, a high variety of volatiles belonging to the chemical classes of aldehydes and sulfides are formed when amino acids undergo reduction, dehydrogenation, decarboxylation, and transamination (Smit et al., 2009). An example of such aldehydes formed under these conditions is the branched-chain aldehydes 2- and 3-methylbutanal, which are formed primarily from leucine and isoleucine as substrates, amino acids that are present as a result of enzymatic activity intrinsic to the legume or produced by microorganisms (Smit et al., 2009).

Like trypsin inhibitors, “beany” off-flavor compounds are undesirable, meaning traditional processing has been used to reduce them. These conventional processing methods involve targeting the enzymes involved in lipid oxidation. Thermal treatment can, like with trypsin inhibitors, also be used to inactivate lipoxygenase, which, as described earlier, is a key enzyme in hexanal formation (Henderson et al., 1991). This is exemplified by the findings of (Lv et al., 2011), where “beany” off-flavor volatile compounds, such as hexanal, were significantly reduced by hot water treatments (above 80°C), which was further linked to a reduction in lipoxygenase activity.

1.4 Traditional processing methods and their limitations

As both off-flavor and antinutrients limit broad consumer acceptance of plant-based protein products, legumes often go through intensive processing methods to reduce these undesirable features. These methods include physical processing like soaking, dehulling the seeds, and thermal treatments such as cooking, blanching, roasting, and boiling. Also, chemical processes have been employed, such as reducing agents and the use of acids and bases (Avilés-Gaxiola et al., 2018; Fischer et al., 2022).

These conventional methods are effective at reducing/inactivating undesirable compounds and have the advantage of being fully standardized and scalable. However, they also have disadvantages that clash with the societal desire and demand for sustainable food production. Firstly, the conventional processing methods are energy-demanding, requiring a huge consumption of electricity and water. Secondly, many of these processing methods reduce or have a negative impact on the nutritional profile of legumes, resulting in loss of key minerals, reduction of B-vitamins, worsening the level of certain amino acids, and changes to the colour of the legume. These disadvantages are not taken lightly, especially as the nutritional profile of plant-based protein products is already challenged. Lastly, consumers in the modern age are looking for products that are as “natural” as possible, viewing processed foods in a negative light. With all this in mind, alternative methods for the optimisation of legumes are gaining more traction. One alternative and promising method that could be a solution is microbial fermentation, which is the process this project revolves around (Avilés-Gaxiola et al., 2018; Fischer et al., 2022).

1.5 Microbial fermentation

Fermentation is a type of metabolism carried out by a vast array of microorganisms. Its definition varies, but at its core, it is a catabolic process, where organic compounds act as both electron donors and acceptors, with the result being the generation of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) in the absence of oxygen (Hackmann & Zhang, 2023). The energy-producing ability without requiring oxygen lies at the core of the ecology of certain microorganisms, such as obligate and facultative anaerobes, which enables them to occupy oxygen-poor environments like the gastrointestinal tract. This stands in contrast to aerobic respiration, which produces significantly more ATP (Hackmann & Zhang, 2023; W. Liu et al., 2025). Moreover, both the substrates and end products (Figure 4) also vary depending on the specific microorganism and environmental conditions:

Figure 4: Overview of common compounds found as substrates during fermentation (Hackmann, 2024)

Figure 5: End products commonly formed as a result of fermentation (Hackmann & Zhang, 2023).

The microbial metabolic definition given above is effective and accepted within microbial ecology. However, this definition becomes too limiting in the case of food fermentation and fermented foods. Here, a broader definition is needed. Firstly, because many aerobic processes are relevant and found in the context of food fermentation, which contradicts the metabolic definition of fermentation as an anaerobic process. Secondly, reactions not resulting in the generation of ATP are also common (Auchtung et al., 2025; Hackmann & Zhang, 2023), with the reason being that fermentation in a food context deals with the transformation of food into

a “desired” state and not a strictly biochemical definition of “ATP-generation”. Food fermentation is largely about improving the product through the modulation of aroma compounds and texture (Marco et al., 2021). This is exemplified by koji fermentation, where the ability of fungi to produce extracellular proteolytic and amylolytic enzymes is critical. These secreted enzymes break down components found in the food, resulting in flavor and color changes. For example, proteins get broken down into amino acids by the proteolytic enzymes, resulting in umami taste (Diez-Simon et al., 2020). Therefore, fermented foods were defined as “made through desired microbial growth and enzymatic conversions of food components” (Marco et al., 2021).

No matter the definition, fermentation’s ability to modulate the food matrix through harnessing the metabolism of certain microorganisms has been studied and utilized thoroughly. This modulating of the compounds within food results in better texture, an improved aroma/flavor profile, and a reduction in undesirable attributes (W. Liu et al., 2025). These positive, transformative capabilities are what this thesis will investigate by employing four different food-relevant microorganisms to evaluate their capacity to ferment faba beans in mono-culture and co-cultures. These four are two lactic acid bacteria (LAB), *Bacillus subtilis* var. *natto*, and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

1.6 Lactic Acid Bacteria

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are an extremely diverse group of food-relevant microorganisms taxonomically belonging to the order *Lactobacillales* within the phylum *Bacillota*. These bacteria are characterised by the following features: Gram-positive, non-spore-forming, non-motile rods or cocci. Furthermore, they possess the ability to be acid-tolerant, allowing them to dominate acidic environments, which, together with their metabolism, is one of the reasons they are highly important as starter cultures and for food fermentation in general (Gänzle, 2015; Orla-Jensen, 1919; Papadimitriou et al., 2016; Zheng et al., 2020).

Regarding their metabolism, the group is known for its ability to produce a variety of organic acids, mainly lactic acid, as the main or singular end product during carbohydrate fermentation. Based on this, LAB are crudely classified into two groups based on their metabolism (Gänzle, 2015; Punia Bangar et al., 2022).

Figure 6: Simplified visualization of the difference between homofermentative (left) and heterofermentative (right) metabolism of glucose in LAB (Caplice & Fitzgerald, 1999).

Firstly, during homofermentative metabolism (Figure 6, left), glucose is broken down to pyruvate as a result of glycolysis. Following this, the enzyme lactate dehydrogenase reduces pyruvate to lactate, which regenerates 2 NAD^+ from 2 $NADH$ granting the glycolysis with the necessary components for continuation. Ultimately, this process ends up producing one main product (lactate) and yielding 2 ATP per glucose (Gänzle, 2015; Kandler, 1983).

Secondly, some LAB possess heterofermentative metabolism (Figure 6, right). Here, in contrast to the homofermentative pathway, the pathway can end up with multiple different end products such as lactate, carbon dioxide, and acetate. Lactate can, like in the homofermentative pathway, be formed by reducing pyruvate via lactate dehydrogenase. However, the difference lies in the start of the metabolism, where the phosphoketolase pathway takes place, resulting in the formation of acetyl phosphate, which is converted into acetyl-CoA and further converted to acetaldehyde, regenerating 1 NAD^+ from 1 $NADH$. Lastly, acetaldehyde is transformed to ethanol via alcohol dehydrogenase, again regenerating 1 $NADH$ to 1 NAD^+ . This process results only in 1 ATP being produced per glucose, however the heterofermentative metabolism can generate 2 ATP per sugar molecule if the starting point is pentose. In this instance of substrate phosphorylation, acetylphosphate transfers a phosphate group to ADP, generating ATP and acetate (Gänzle, 2015; Kandler, 1983).

In this project, two species of LAB are employed, namely *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* and *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*.

1.6.1 *Limosilactobacillus fermentum*

Members of the *Limosilactobacillus* genus are obligate heterofermentative, anaerobic or aerotolerant, rod- or cocci-shaped bacteria that have the capacity to ferment a diverse range of carbohydrates, with most strains in the genus being isolated from intestinal habitats. However, strains of this project's species *L. fermentum* are unlike other members of the genus, adapted, found, and isolated within spontaneously fermented cereals and other plant-based fermentation products (Zheng et al., 2020).

1.6.2 *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*

Like *L. fermentum*, species of the genus *Lactiplantibacillus* are isolated and found in fermented foods. Furthermore, they share similarities with members of *Limosilactobacillus* in that they can also ferment a vast array of carbohydrates. However, differences between the two genera also exist. Firstly, the species of *Lactiplantibacillus* are facultative heterofermentative, meaning that the main metabolic pathway is the homofermentative, however, situationally, the heterofermentative pathway can be induced. Secondly, the cells are exclusively rod-shaped. Third and lastly, *L. plantarum* is a microorganism that has been studied much more extensively as it holds high importance within food fermentation as a starter culture and as a probiotic (Gökmen et al., 2024; Zheng et al., 2020).

1.6.3 The capacity of LAB to optimize legume quality

When it comes to optimizing legumes through fermentation, both species show promising results. From the perspective of antinutrients, it has already been demonstrated that LAB have the ability to reduce the content of trypsin inhibitors in legumes. In *Phaseolus vulgaris* (common bean), it has been shown that fermentation with *L. fermentum* at 37°C for 72 h results in a reduction of 38.77 % for raw beans and 34.35 % for soaked beans (Barampama & Simard, 1994). Likewise, it has also been shown that *L. plantarum* can significantly reduce the trypsin inhibitor content in legumes. This has been observed in soybean, where fermentation with *L. plantarum* for 5 days showed a reduction of 99.2 %, matching the effects of cooking and roasting, which showed reductions of 95.8 % and 98.3 %, respectively (Adeyemo & Onilude, 2013). Additionally, other findings match these effects, showing that fermentation of soybean meals with *L. plantarum* resulted in a reduction of 88.9 % (Chi & Cho, 2016).

With respect to improving the sensory profile of legume products, both *L. fermentum* and *L. plantarum* have been shown to reduce the “beany” off-flavor and improve the global aroma profile (Zheng et al., 2020). An example of this is the findings of (Schindler et al., 2011), where fermentation of *Lupinus angustifolius* (sweet lupin) protein extracts with *L. plantarum* resulted in a significantly changed aroma profile. Furthermore, the findings show a reduction in hexanal concentration and prevention of regeneration during storage. Equally, fermentation for 24 h at 37°C with *L. fermentum* was shown to reduce the relative content of hexanal in both soy and peanut milk, resulting in the reduction of “beany” off-flavor and improvement in the global aroma profile (Meng et al., 2023).

1.7 *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

S. cerevisiae, also known as brewer’s yeast, is a facultative anaerobic eukaryotic fungal microorganism that has significant relevance within food fermentation. As the microorganism is a facultative anaerobe, it has the ability to perform fermentation in anaerobic conditions. However, it can also utilize aerobic respiration when oxygen is present (Figure 7) (Bai et al., 2022).

In aerobic respiration (Figure 7, left), pyruvate is converted to acetyl-CoA as a result of oxidative decarboxylation. This triggers the TCA cycle, a mitochondrial metabolic pathway, whose goal is to produce NADH and FADH₂. These coenzymes/electron carriers are integral to the electron transport chain, where they help create a proton gradient, which ultimately ends up generating ATP through oxidative phosphorylation (Piškur et al., 2006; Zhou et al., 2017).

However, *S. cerevisiae* preferentially performs fermentation even when oxygen is present and when glucose concentrations are high, an ability known as the Crabtree effect (De Deken, 1966). In the alcoholic fermentation pathway (Figure 7), which is the most standard and most influential from a food fermentation perspective, pyruvate is converted into acetaldehyde, producing carbon dioxide in the process. This is the first step, followed by the reduction of acetaldehyde to ethanol catalysed by alcohol dehydrogenase. This pathway results in two molecules of ATP, which is significantly lower than the ATP yield during aerobic respiration (Piškur et al., 2006; Zhou et al., 2017).

Figure 7: Simplified scheme of glucose metabolism found within *S. cerevisiae*. Left: aerobic respiration pathway. Right: fermentation pathway *cerevisiae* (Fischer et al., 2022).

1.7.1 The capacity of *S. cerevisiae* to optimize legume quality

The microorganism is known to improve the overall aroma profile of food matrices through fermentation, as it plays a critical role in the production of “positive” aromatic flavor compounds, primarily alcohols and esters (Tao et al., 2022). This is exemplified during the fermentation of grapes in wine production. Here, the production of the highly important esters is essential, as they contribute to the floral and fruity aroma (Parapouli et al., 2020). However, *S. cerevisiae* has also been shown to reduce “negative” volatile compounds, such as aldehydes like (E)-2-hexenal, (Z)-3-hexenal, and hexanal. This was shown by (Fauconnier et al., 1999), where living yeast cells were able to convert (Z)-3-hexenal into (Z)-3-hexenol through their production of alcohol dehydrogenase, thereby reducing the concentration of the aldehyde. Moreover, a similar finding was also shown with regard to hexanal, however, here, commercially bought alcohol dehydrogenase from *S. cerevisiae* was used. Furthermore, *S. cerevisiae* not only has the ability to affect the aroma profile but has also been shown to reduce the level of antinutrients. (Chi & Cho, 2016) showed that fermentation of soybean meal with *S. cerevisiae* reduced the level of trypsin inhibitors by 73.8 %.

1.8 *Bacillus subtilis*

The species *Bacillus subtilis* is an aerobic, Gram-positive, rod-shaped, fast-growing, motile bacterium, which is found in a multitude of environments. For example, it is a commonly found member of the plant microbiome, especially with regard to the rhizosphere. The bacterium is also spore-forming, possessing the ability to produce endospores, which are exceedingly resistant, serving as a response to unfavourable environmental conditions like extreme temperatures, nutrient depletion, to name a few stressors. Additionally, *B. subtilis* is also known for the ability to create biofilms of complex architectural structure (Earl, Losick and Kolter, no date; Branda et al., 2001; Errington and van der Aa, 2020).

This project employs the strain *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, a strain that is the microorganism responsible for natto, a traditional Japanese dish consisting of fermented soybeans. The ability of this bacterium to modulate the sensory and nutritional profile of legumes is well known. *B. subtilis* var. *natto* plays an integral role in food fermentation, coming from its significant capacity to degrade carbohydrates, lipids, and especially proteins. *B. subtilis* shows high proteolytic activity as the species possesses the ability to produce and secrete a vast range of proteases. Its proteolytic arsenal consists of both a high number of extracellular and intracellular proteases (Harwood & Kikuchi, 2022; Jiang et al., 2020). Extracellular proteases are enzymes secreted by *B. subtilis* to acquire nutrients in environments where the nutrients are contained in large/complex structures. These enzymes have the capacity to degrade proteins extracellularly, and *B. subtilis* is known to produce eight types of such proteases, where the majority belong to the peptidase S8 protein family (Rosazza et al., 2023).

1.8.1 The capacity of *B. subtilis* to optimize legume quality

Strains of *B. subtilis* have already been shown to effectively degrade trypsin inhibitors. This was, for example, shown by (Qi et al., 2024), where 24 and 48 hours of solid-state fermentation of soybean meal with *B. subtilis* L5 resulted in degradation of trypsin inhibitors. Furthermore, the findings also indicate positive results regarding other antinutritional factors like phytic acid, effective antimicrobial capacities against the undesirable Gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), as well as an increase in concentration of free amino acids and crude protein (Qi et al., 2024).

Furthermore, its effect on volatile aroma compounds can be seen by comparing the volatile compounds between unfermented soybeans and fermented natto. Here, fermentation leads to a significant increase in ketones, alcohols, and esters. Moreover, aldehydes significantly decreased, which includes hexanal and contributes most to the “beany” off-flavor.

1.9 Microbial communities and interactions within fermentation

In the sections above, the characteristics and abilities of three types of microorganisms when applied as mono-cultures within food fermentation were described. However, many fermented foods rely on the interactions between several different types of microorganisms spanning across vast taxonomic levels, including species, orders, and even domains. These interactions occur within complex microbial communities, either assembled intentionally using starter cultures or “naturally” by the resident microbiota existing in the raw food material. Utilizing the resident microbiota introduces a variety of factors, as the composition is influenced by geography, climate, processing methods, and environments. Regardless of the assembly method, these interactions are influenced by a variety of factors such as pH, salinity, antimicrobials, and redox potential, and the usability of fermentation substrates, all factors as abiotic (Auchtung et al., 2025).

As for biotic factors, here the focus switches to the different interactions between the microorganisms during the fermentation process. These interactions can be classified depending on the ecological effects on the participating microorganisms of the interactions. Thus, four different classifications will be introduced as they are relevant and classic examples found within fermentation (Auchtung et al., 2025; W. Liu et al., 2025).

1.9.1 Amensalisms

Amensalism is an interaction between microorganisms where inhibition of one occurs, however one remains unaffected. This can be a result of the production of metabolites possessing inhibitory qualities, which is an effective way of ensuring that the fermentation process is performed by the intended microorganisms (W. Liu et al., 2025). This can be exemplified by the findings of (Delbes-Paus et al., 2010), where during fermentation of raw milk, the production of hydrogen peroxide by *Lactococcus garvieae* inhibited the growth of

Staphylococcus aureus. This interaction ultimately leads to an increase in food safety as the presence of the pathogenic *S. aureus* is undesirable due to its ability to cause food poisoning. Moreover, amensalism can also manifest as the removal of compounds by one microorganism that would be usable by another microorganism, thereby leading to inhibition of the latter. An example of this occurs in fermented milk products where LAB, via competitive exclusion, scavenges manganese, resulting in the inhibition of various molds and yeast (Siedler et al., 2020).

1.9.2 Competition

Where amensalism results in asymmetric inhibition, the inhibitory consequences of competition affect both microorganisms. Competition can be divided into two classes, exploitative and interference, with the two differing in their suppression mechanism. In the instance of exploitative competition, the mechanism revolves around the non-intentional inhibition that occurs when microorganisms compete for limited resources and space in an environment. As for interference, here microorganisms actively suppress the growth of other microorganisms through the production of specialized metabolites with antimicrobial properties like antibiotics and bacteriocins, which both inhibit the growth of competitors (Chang & Chang, 2011; Stubbendieck & Straight, 2016).

Specifically, bacteriocins, which are antimicrobial peptides that are produced by a vast array of bacteria, including food-relevant microorganisms like LAB. In the context of food microbiology, this group of compounds has gained attention as possible food preservatives. Most bacteriocins have a narrow inhibitory spectrum, meaning they target phylogenetically related bacteria (Xu et al., 2025). Bacteriocins vary in their mode of action, as exemplified by LAB bacteriocins. Firstly, they can cause pore formation in their target's cytoplasmic membrane. Secondly, they can bind to lipid II, resulting in inhibition of cell-wall synthesis. Lastly, other examples include the triggering of autolysis and the ability to inhibit spores from germinating (Pérez-Ramos et al., 2021). Furthermore, the production of bacteriocins is linked to quorum sensing, a communication system that relies on cell density. Here, each individual cell produces quorum-sensing molecules called autoinducers, whose concentration/accumulation increases as cell density increases, leading to a response, which could be the production of bacteriocins (Man & Xiang, 2023).

1.9.3 Commensalism

Commensal interactions are characterized as positively affecting one microorganism, whereas the other microorganism is unaffected. This can happen when one microorganism produces a metabolite during its growth, which then, in turn, can be utilized by another microorganism, resulting in the growth of the latter as well. Additionally, it can also happen in a scenario where one microorganism consumes and removes a compound from the environment that was inhibiting the growth of another microorganism. This removal then allows for better growth of the previously inhibited microorganism (W. Liu et al., 2025). Commensal interactions are relevant when it comes to improving the sensory profile of fermented foods. Such an example can be seen in the production of hard cheese. Here, the interaction between LAB and *Propionibacterium freudenreichii* is a commensal one as the LAB prepares the cheese for propionic acid fermentation by converting lactose found in the milk to lactate, which *P. freudenreichii* consumes and produces propionate (Kerjean et al., 2000).

1.9.4 Mutualism

Finally, there is mutualism, which is characterized by both microorganisms benefiting. This is further highlighted by a phenomenon observed during these interactions where the microorganisms are “living and dying together”. This underlines the necessity and dependency the individual microorganisms have upon each other, as the individuals lack the ability to produce essential compounds needed for survival by themselves. As a response, they have adapted to rely on acquiring these compounds from the metabolism of other microorganisms. This type of interaction is prevalent within food fermentation, where the exchange of signalling molecules and intermediate metabolites results in enhancement of metabolic end products, alteration of gene expression, and activation of metabolic pathways (W. Liu et al., 2025).

A key example of mutualism is found in sourdough fermentation, where the mutualistic interaction between the lactic acid bacterium *Fructilactobacillus sanfranciscensis* and yeast species like *S. cerevisiae* and *Kazachstania exigu*a is based on fundamental metabolic capabilities. Yeast releases amino acids and peptides during growth and autolysis, which cross-feed *L. sanfranciscensis*, stimulating growth. Additionally, the stability of the interaction is kept intact by the differing carbohydrate preferences of the two microorganisms. *L. sanfranciscensis* prefers maltose, while the yeast *K. exigu*a prefers glucose or sucrose, creating

a scenario where the two do not compete for the same sugar. Furthermore, after uptake of maltose *L. sanfranciscensis* breaks down the sugar to glucose-1-phosphate, which it uses for itself and glucose, which it transports out of the cell, providing the yeast with its preferred sugar source. Lastly, *K. exiqa* exhibits high tolerance to the acetic acid produced by the heterofermentative pathway of *L. sanfranciscensis*. These examples emphasise the adaptations and reliance of two microorganisms within one fermentation setting (Gobbetti & Corsetti, 1997).

2. Aims and Objectives

Plant-based protein sources are in high demand as the transition toward sustainable food production is needed to mitigate current environmental and climate issues. Legumes have gained traction as a solution, with faba beans presenting themselves as a promising candidate. However, widespread consumption of faba beans is limited by off-flavor compounds and antinutrients (Lumsden et al., 2024; Mayer Labba et al., 2021; Ritter et al., 2024).

Microbial fermentation of legumes shows promise as a sustainable alternative to traditional methods for mitigating these two undesirable attributes. Therefore, a deeper understanding of microbial fermentation of faba beans could contribute to the advancement of more sustainable food production (Avilés-Gaxiola et al., 2018; Fischer et al., 2022).

By utilizing *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, all strains that belong to species that have shown promise in other legume-based fermentations (Adeyemo & Onilude, 2013; Barampama & Simard, 1994; Chi & Cho, 2016; Qi et al., 2024), this master's thesis aims to explore microbial fermentation of faba bean by:

- Assessing the ability of *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto* to ferment and grow on faba beans in mono-cultures and co-cultures using both a liquid and a solid-state fermentation system.
- Examining the interactions between the four food-relevant microorganisms through in-vitro interaction assays.
- Testing whether fermentation with the four food-relevant microorganisms can reduce trypsin inhibitor activity in faba beans by conducting a trypsin inhibitor assay.
- Evaluating if fermentation with the four food-relevant microorganisms can shift the VOC profile of faba beans via GC-MS, with a focus on whether the strains can reduce the concentration of aldehydes associated with “beany” off-flavors.
- To investigate whether confocal microscopy can be used to visualize the structural and compositional changes in faba beans following microbial fermentation.

3. Materials and methods

3.1 Strains, culturing/maintenance, and chemicals

3.1.1 Strains

Eight strains were used during this project. One strain was *Bacillus subtilis* var. *natto*, which was acquired through commercial natto spores (LUVI fermente KG, Lenzing, Austria). Another being *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* NCYC 625 (NCYC 625 - *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae* | *National Collection of Yeast Cultures*, n.d.). The rest of them were LAB strains, all previously isolated from different foods and locations. An overview of all strains can be seen in the table below:

Strain	Food source	Location
<i>limosilactobacillus fermentum</i> UFLA CH-13	Cocoa pods	Itajuípe, Bahia State, Brazil
<i>limosilactobacillus fermentum</i> 20-8	Nunu, fermented yogurt-like milk product	Upper east region of Ghana
<i>limosilactobacillus fermentum</i> 24H6H2	Mawé, fermented maize dough	Southern Benin
<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i> 2-1	Nunu, fermented yogurt-like milk product	Upper east region of Ghana
<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i> L106	Cocoa beans	Ghana
<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i> 36H8H1	Mawé, fermented maize dough	Southern Benin
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> NCYC 625	Unknown	Unkown
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> var. <i>natto</i>	Commercial natto spores	Commercial natto spores

3.1.2 Culture media

The following media were used for the cultivation of strains used in this thesis. All media were made with deionized water, and for the making of agar plates, media were supplemented with (20 g/L) agar powder except in the case of soft agar, where (7 g/L) was used. To achieve sterility, all media were autoclaved, and for control plates, (17.5 g/L) plate counting agar (PCA) was dissolved in deionized water.

LAB were cultivated using Man, Rogosa Sharpe (MRS) medium, which was prepared by dissolving (55.15 g/L) of MRS broth in deionized water.

For the cultivation of *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, malt extract, yeast extract, glucose, and peptone (MYGP) liquid medium was used, which consisted of (3 g/L) malt extract, (3 g/L) yeast extract, (10 g/L) glucose, and peptone (5 g/L) dissolved in deionized water. During co-culture experiments, MYGP medium was supplemented with (100 mg/L) chloramphenicol and (50 mg/L) chlortetracycline to prevent the growth of bacteria.

Finally, the cultivation of *B. subtilis* var. *natto* was done in Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) liquid medium, which was prepared from (37 g/L) BHI broth suspended in deionized water.

3.1.3 Culture/inoculum preparations

Before each experiment, strains were streaked aseptically from 20 % glycerol stocks kept at 60 °C onto the following agar media: LAB strains were grown on MRS agar and incubated anaerobically at 30 °C for 48 h. Anaerobic conditions were achieved by adding a Thermo Scientific™ Oxoid™ AnaeroGen™ 2.5 L sachet to an anaerobic chamber. *B. subtilis* var. *natto* was streaked on BHI agar and incubated at 30 °C for 16-18 h. Finally, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 was grown on MYGP agar and incubated at 30 °C for 48 h.

For the preparation of overnight/liquid cultures, a single isolated colony from a plate as described above was transferred using a sterile inoculation loop into the strain's corresponding liquid medium and incubated under the same conditions as previously described. However, cultures of *B. subtilis* var. *natto* and *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 were incubated with shaking, and LAB grew aerobically.

3.1.4 Chemicals for trypsin inhibitor assay

For the trypsin inhibitor assay, the following chemicals were used: 10 mM NaOH solution (sodium hydroxide) was prepared by dissolving 0.39997 g in 1 L of deionized water. 1 mM HCL (hydrochloric acid) with 5 mM CaCl₂ was prepared by dissolving 0.736 g CaCl₂·2H₂O in 900 mL deionized water, after which 0,5 ml 2 M HCL was added and diluted to 1 mL with deionized water. pH was then adjusted to 3,0±0,2. Tris buffer 50 mM containing 20 mM CaCl₂ (pH 8.2) was made by dissolving 2.94 g CaCl₂·2H₂O and 6.05 g Tris (hydroxymethyl) aminomethane in 900 mL deionised water, after which pH was adjusted to 8.2 with 2M HCL and finally diluted to 1000 mL with deionised water. Acetic acid solution was made by mixing 30 mL of glacial acetic acid with 70 mL of deionised water (30% v/v).

10 mg of trypsin from bovine pancreas was dissolved in the HCL solution to achieve a 0.2 mg/mL stock solution. From this, a working solution of 20 µg/mL was made by diluting the stock solution to 25 ml with the HCL solution.

A BAPA stock solution 40mg/mL was prepared by dissolving 200 mg DL-BAPA (Na-Benzoyl-DL-arginine 4-nitroanilide hydrochloride) in 5 mL DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide). 0.5 of this stock solution was further diluted to 50 mL with Tris buffer to create a BAPA 0.4 mg/ml working solution.

3.2 Faba bean fermentations

To assess the ability of the different microbial strains, in both mono-culture and co-culture, to grow on and ferment faba beans, two different fermentation methods/media were employed. Furthermore, the samples collected after the different fermentations were subsequently used to evaluate the impact on functional properties.

3.3.1 Fermentation media

All fermentations were conducted on Danish dehulled organic faba beans (*Vicia faba*) from the brand Biogan A/S. From these faba beans, two fermentation media were deployed: a liquid medium and a solid-state medium. The liquid medium was prepared by milling the whole faba

beans into a powder and dissolving it in sterile MiliQ water. Whereas the solid-state medium consisted of the whole beans as they were sold commercially. Both media underwent gamma radiation to achieve sterility.

3.2.2 Liquid fermentation

Aseptically, 10 g of sterilized milled faba bean powder was hydrated with 90 mL sterilized Mili-Q water (10% w/v) in a sterile 250 mL conical flask, mixing using a sterile magnetic stir. One flask constitutes one sample.

After hydrating the medium, 5 mL of the prepared overnight liquid culture (see culture preparation) was transferred into a sterile 15 mL Falcon tube, which was then centrifuged for 10 min at ~ 4500 rcf. The supernatant was removed and replaced with an equal volume of sterile 0,9 NaCl solution, followed by resuspending the pellet. The inoculums were then diluted to achieve an OD600 measurement in the range of 0.1-0.8. Based on the measured OD600 values for each strain/inoculum, the volume needed to inoculate each conical flask to a concentration of 10^5 CFU/mL for LAB and 10^4 CFU/mL for *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and *B. subtilis* var. *natto* was calculated. Each strain was then inoculated into its corresponding flask, except the 0 h control and 48 control flasks, which received no inoculation. Finally, the flasks were incubated at 30°C for 48 h with 120 rpm shaking.

After each flask had undergone its designated fermentation time, 1 mL was transferred aseptically into a sterile Eppendorf tube from which viable/CFU counts were measured. Additionally, the liquid medium was also transferred to a 50 ml Falcon tube for pH measurement. The remaining liquid medium was distributed into 50 mL Falcon tubes and kept at -60°C until needed for analysis.

3.2.3 Solid-state fermentation

In a sterile bottle, dry faba beans were soaked with sterile Milli-Q water (1:2 w/v) for 17 hours at 4°C. Afterwards, the soaked beans were decanted of excess water, and 25 g of the soaked beans were transferred aseptically to a sterile petri dish, constituting one sample.

5 mL of the prepared overnight liquid culture (see culture preparation) was transferred into a sterile 15 mL Falcon tube, which was then centrifuged for 10 min at ~ 4500 rcf. The supernatant

was removed and replaced with an equal volume of sterile 0.9 NaCl solution, followed by resuspending the pellet. The inoculums were then diluted to achieve an OD600 measurement in the range of 0.1-0.8. Each strain inoculum was then diluted to reach a concentration of 10^5 CFU/mL for LAB and 10^4 CFU/mL for *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*.

Each petri dish was then inoculated with 1 mL and mixed for 2 min to ensure equal coating for each singular bean. For co-fermentation, the inoculum was adjusted to 10^5 CFU/0.5mL for LAB and 10^4 CFU/0.5mL for *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. Two strains were therefore inoculated with 0.5 mL each and mixed. In both mono and co-fermentations, 0 h and 48 h controls received no inoculation.

After inoculation, the petri dishes (Appendix 10) were incubated for 48 h at 30°C. Following the designated fermentation time, the petri dishes (Appendix 10) were taken out for sampling. Aseptically, 2.5 grams were taken out and transferred to a stomacher bag, adding sterile Milli-Q water to make a 10-fold dilution. The bag was placed in the stomacher machine for 1 minute at normal speed. Afterwards, from the bag, 1 mL was taken out, from which viable/CFU counts were measured. Around 2.5-3 g was then retrieved and mixed with MilliQ water in a 1:1 (w/v) ratio and vortexed for 20 seconds before measuring pH. The rest of the fermented beans were placed into 50 mL falcons and stored at -80°C until needed for analysis.

3.2.4 Measurements of viable counts/CFU and pH

Viable counts/CFU from fermentation samples were measured by transferring 100 μ L of cell suspension to a 10-fold dilution series made in 1.5 mL sterile Eppendorf tubes filled with 900 μ L sterile 0.9 NaCl solution. Three serial dilutions, depending on strain and time point, were then plated out onto MRS agar medium for LAB strains, MYGP medium for *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and BHI medium for *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, which were finally incubated under conditions described under culture/inoculum preparations. After incubation, the plates were taken out, and the CFU was counted, which was used to calculate CFU/mL or CFU/g using the formula below:

$$\frac{(\text{number of colonies} \cdot \text{dillution factor})}{\text{volume of cell suspension plated}}$$

The pH of the samples was measured using a Radiometer PHM 250 Ion Analyzer.

3.3 In vitro assays for investigating the interactions between strains

An understanding of the interactions between the four different microbial strains deployed would further an understanding of their roles within the fermentation of faba beans.

Therefore, a spot agar assay was performed to reveal potential antagonistic/inhibitory interactions. Afterwards, a well diffusion assay was performed to determine potential underlying mechanisms.

3.3.1 Spot agar assay

Overnight liquid culture (see culture preparation) was placed on ice, and each strain was adjusted to an $OD_{600} = 10^7$ CFU/mL. The adjusted strains were then spotted on their preferred (see culture preparation) agar medium by placing one spot of 3 μ L in the middle of the plate or 3 spots distributed evenly across the plate, both plate scenarios also containing a 3 μ L spot of negative control (sterile liquid media). This was followed by incubating the plates for 24-48 h, depending on the tested interactions at 30 °C.

After incubation, 0.7% soft agar was inoculated to a concentration of 10^5 CFU/mL, from which 8 mL was poured onto the plates containing the spot of the producer, after which the plates stayed upright to solidify before being inverted and incubated at 30°C. After the designated incubation time, the plates were taken out, and if present, the inhibition zone was measured using the formula below.

$$A = \pi \cdot r^2$$

$$\text{Inhibition zone} = A_{\text{colony+inhibiton zone}} - A_{\text{colony}}$$

soft agar with inoculation of indicator

Figure 8: Visualization of spot agar assay. Modified from (Fijan, 2016).

3.3.2 Well Diffusion Assay

A petri dish containing nutrient agar was covered with 6 mL 0.7 % soft agar inoculated with 10^5 CFU/mL of the intended indicator microorganism. After the lawn had solidified, wells were made using a sterilised plunger. These wells were then filled with cell-free supernatant (CFS).

CFS was acquired by centrifuging 1 mL of an overnight liquid culture (see culture preparation) of producer microorganisms for 10 min at 5000 rpm. The supernatant was then aseptically collected and transferred into a sterile 1.5 Eppendorf tube via a syringe attached with a 0.20 μ m filter, removing any microorganisms. This was followed by adding proteinase K to some of the samples (50 μ L to 500 μ L supernatant) and leaving those samples covered on the heating block at 57 °C for 30 min. Finally, a single petri dish with a lawn of an indicator microorganism contained wells with the following content per producer (3 producers per petri dish) microorganism tested:

- 1 well with 30 μ L CFS
- 1 well with 30 μ L CFS 50% diluted
- 1 well with 30 μ L CFS 50% diluted + Proteinase K (20mg/mL)
- 1 well containing sterile liquid media (negative control)

Figure 9: Visualization of the well diffusion assay. Modified from (Fijan, 2016).

The petri dishes were incubated upright at 30 °C for 24 h and 48 h. At each time point, the petri dishes were taken out and examined. A positive result was noted if an inhibition zone around a well was observed.

3.4 Assessment of functional properties after fermentation

After having conducted fermentations with the previously described microbial strains, the subsequent aim was to explore the effects of the fermentations on the aroma profile and antinutritional properties of faba beans. With respect to the effects on the content of antinutrients, here, trypsin inhibitors were used as a representative class of antinutrients, and the levels were examined through a trypsin inhibitor assay. Regarding the impact on the aroma profile, this was conducted on samples from SSF via gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS).

3.4.1 Trypsin Inhibitor Assay

To assess the level of trypsin inhibitors, samples from the different fermentations were taken out of -60°C storage and freeze-dried for a duration of approximately 72 h. After, the samples were ground down with a mortar until a uniform powder was achieved. Following this, 0.5 g of the sample was weighed and transferred to a conical flask, to which 25 mL of 10 mM NaOH solution was added and covered with parafilm. Extraction was then preceded by shaking the samples at 500 rpm for 3 h at room temperature. After extraction, the samples were used for trypsin inhibitor analysis right away or kept overnight at 4 °C.

For the trypsin inhibitor analysis, reagent solutions were added to 15 mL Falcon tubes in the exact sequence and volumes as described below, maintaining the same intervals between each sample and being conducted in a water bath at 37 °C, and vortexing for 10 s after adding each reagent.

Sample overview:

- Sample reading 1 (A_{410S1})
- Sample reading 2 (A_{410S2})
- Sample blank (A_{410SB})
- Reference reading 1 (A_{410R1})
- Reference reading 2 (A_{410R2})
- Reference reading blank (A_{410RB})

Addition sequence:

1. 1 mL diluted sample suspension (deionised water for reference samples)
2. 2.5 mL BAPA working solution
3. 0.5 mL acetic acid solution to the blank samples
4. 1 mL trypsin working solution after a 10 min timer was started
5. After 10 minutes, 0.5 mL of acetic acid solution was added to the samples to stop the colorimetric reaction.

After all the samples were centrifuged for 5 min at 1500 rcf, which was followed by measuring the absorbance of each sample's supernatant at 410 nm (using deionised water as a reference). Using the measured absorbance, the % inhibition was calculated, and a sample was determined usable if the % inhibition was between 30%-70%. Finally, the trypsin units inhibited (TUI) per mg sample was calculated using the following formula:

$$A_{410S} \text{ corrected} = \left(\frac{A_{410S1} - A_{410S2}}{2} \right) - A_{410B}$$

$$TUI = \frac{A_{410R} \text{ corrected} - A_{410S} \text{ corrected}}{0.02}$$

$$\text{mg of sample in assay} = \frac{\text{sample weight (mg)}}{\text{volume used in extraction}} - \frac{\text{volume dilluted sample used in analysis}}{\text{dillution factor}}$$

$$TUI \text{mg}^{-1} = \frac{TUI}{\text{mg of sample}}$$

3.4.2 Measuring volatile organic compounds on solid-state fermentation samples via GC-MS

To measure the volatile organic compounds (VOCs) from the SSF samples, GC-MS was performed. The method employed was modified by the procedure described by (Larsen et al., 2026). Firstly, headspace sampling was performed as a necessary step for conducting GC-MS analysis. This was achieved by combining 5 g of beans from SSF, 15 ml of deionized water, and 1 ml of 5 ppm internal standard (4-methyl-1-pentanol, 5 mg/L) in a 100 ml flask. This was followed by homogenizing the solution for 1 min using an ULTRA-TURRAX disperser at 13.2

g. The samples then underwent purging with nitrogen (149 mL/min) at 37°C, stirring with a magnet at 250 rpm. The purging consisted of three different phases: 5 min pre-purge, 30 min purge, and 15 min dry purge, ultimately collecting the VOCs on Tenax-TA traps. The captured volatiles were then separated using a DB-Wax capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.5 µm) utilizing an Agilent 7890 A GC system interfaced with a 5975C VL MSD with a Triple-Axis detector (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA) (Larsen et al., 2026).

The data were extracted from the GC-MS procedure via PARADISE software (Quintanilla-Casas et al., 2024). The identification of VOCs were derived from utilizing the retention indices (RI) of n-alkanes (C6–C22) and the NIST05 database. Further confirmation was carried out by comparing the RI of authentic reference compounds or published RI values. The concentration (µg/kg) of each VOC in the analyzed samples was established semi-quantitatively through the normalizing of the peak area for each compound to the internal standard and further multiplying this by the internal standard concentration (Rasconi et al., 2009). Lastly, the PARADISE software determines the quality of each identification. The matches that were determined “poor/no match” were not included in the data analysis. Furthermore, irrelevant alkanes and alkenes were not analysed.

3.5 Preliminary confocal microscopy methodology for visualizing structural changes in faba beans

To visualize the structural impact of the conducted solid-state fermentation on faba beans, confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) was employed in combination with three different dyes. One biological replicate from the mono-culture solid-state fermentations was analysed. This was performed by first taking a single frozen bean (-60°C storage) and placing it in a small plastic container with an optimal cutting temperature (OCT) compound. Next, the container was stored overnight at -20°C overnight to ensure complete freezing. Afterwards, the samples were mounted on a cryostat (Leica CM3050 S) that was conditioned to -25°C. This allowed for sectioning of the samples using a piece of cryofilm (Section-lab) to cover a sample before cutting. Sections were then cut at a thickness of 25 µm with a disposable steel blade.

After the samples were cut, a staining procedure was followed using three different stains. Firstly, Calcofluor white, a fluorochrome that binds to β 1-3 and β 1-4 polysaccharides, which are found in, for example, cellulose or chitin (Rasconi et al., 2009), was used. Secondly, BODIPY was used as an indicator for lipid droplets, as it is a lipophilic molecule that accumulates in the hydrophobic core of lipid droplets, which primarily consists of neutral lipids such as cholesteryl esters and triacylglycerols (Zhu et al., 2024). Lastly, the fluorochrome Rhodamine B was used, as it binds to protein surfaces through non-covalent interactions: hydrogen bonding, electrostatic interactions, and hydrophobic interactions (Ako et al., 2009; Feng et al., 2021).

Each individual staining solution was made by adding 1 μ L of a 1 mg/mL dye stock solution to a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube with 1 mL phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). After, 10 μ L staining solution was applied onto the cryofilm-mounted sample, ensuring the tissue was fully covered. The sample was then left on a petri dish for a duration of 15 min, after which the sample was washed twice with PBS. Next, the sample was moved to a glass slide, and a single drop of 70% glycerol was added. Finally, the sample was covered with a coverslip, and the edges were sealed using clear nail polish. Samples were then analyzed with an inverted CLSM (ZEISS LSM 900, Germany), equipped with Plan-Apochromat 20x/0.8 M27 objective. The images were acquired using 20x, and the size of the images was 120611 x 21658 pixels and 37.63 x 6.76 mm (scaled), with scaling (per pixel) being 0.312 μ m x 0.312 μ m. Lastly, the bit depth was 8 bit.

Three different channels were utilized, corresponding to the three different dyes deployed. The signals of Calcofluor White, Rhodamine B, and BODIPY (shown as blue, red, and green, respectively) were set to laser wavelengths 405 nm, 488 nm, and 561 nm. The maximum excitation and emission wavelengths for Calcofluor white, Rhodamine B, and BODIPY were 400 and 500 nm, 525 and 700 nm, and 410 and 540 nm, respectively. The settings mentioned above remained unchanged across all samples to ensure qualitative comparison. Representative images are shown in the results section.

3.6 Bioinformatical tools

3.6.1 Phylogenetic tree based on the binary presence and absence of accessory genes for selection of LAB strains

To further investigate the possible antagonistic interaction between this project's two LAB species *L. fermentum* and *L. plantarum*, two more strains per species were selected to participate in the spot agar assay and well diffusion assay. The selection of these four new strains was based on a phylogenetic tree based on the binary presence and absence of accessory genes. The tree was made using the genomes annotated with BAKTA (Schwengers et al., 2021), which were subsequently input for pangenome analysis utilizing Roary (Page et al., 2015). Finally, the tree was visualized using (Hadfield et al., 2018)

3.6.2 Measuring the abundance of bacteriocin-relevant genes

To investigate the prevalence of relevant bacteriocin-related genes within the bacterial genomes, an in-house bioinformatic software was used. The software screened genomes annotated with BAKTA (Schwengers et al., 2021), using user-defined keywords matching genes of interest. Keywords could be known names of certain genes or related to functional properties. As a result, for each annotation file given as input, the software extracts “gene abundance”, which is the total number of hits matching the given keyword. The list of specific keywords used to screen for bacteriocin-related genes was generated based on (Xu et al., 2025).

3.6.3 Assessing the number of proteins associated with extracellular proteases

To investigate the extracellular proteolytic capacity of the bacterial strains, a bioinformatic approach including Pfam and HMMER was used. Bacterial genome sequences were first translated into predicted protein sequences, thereby constructing proteomes. A panel of relevant protease families was created using Pfam hidden Markov models (HMMs). Pfam is a protein family database, where each protein family has a seed alignment, from which a profile HMM is constructed (Paysan-Lafosse et al., 2025). Lastly, the proteomes were screened using the `hmmsearch` function from the HMMER software, which is a software that is used to search sequence databases and make sequence alignments using profile HMMs (Paysan-Lafosse et al.,

2025). The output of this approach gives the abundance of proteins that are present within the searched genome containing a domain assigned to a particular protein family. The specific protein families that were screened for were based on the protein families described in (Harwood & Kikuchi, 2022; M. Liu et al., 2010).

3.7 Statistical analysis

All experiments were performed three times independently unless stated otherwise, representing three biological replicates. All analytical data represent the mean \pm standard deviation from the conducted experiment. RStudio was used as software for carrying out statistical analysis, including ANOVA, Tukey's post hoc test, paired t-test, and unpaired t-test, depending on the experiment, all with a significance value of $p < 0.05$. Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed on VOC data acquired from solid-state fermentation to investigate the correlation between the samples and their VOC profiles.

4. Results

The first objective of the project was to assess the four food-relevant microorganisms' ability to ferment/grow on faba beans. This was achieved by using mono-cultures and co-cultures of *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. Furthermore, to assess the growth dynamics during faba bean fermentation, two fermentation systems were used: a liquid and a solid-state. During each fermentation, viable counts (CFU) were measured at inoculation (0 h) and after 48 h, with pH being measured after 48 h for inoculated samples and at 0 h and 48 h for uninoculated controls.

4.1 Growth and pH development in mono- and co-culture liquid and solid-state fermentations of faba beans

First, the four food-relevant microorganisms were deployed as mono-cultures in the liquid and solid-state fermentation systems. The measured viable counts at inoculation (0 h) and after 48 h of fermentation can be seen in Figure 10.

4.1.1 Viable counts/CFU of mono-cultures

Figure 10: Growth of mono-cultures over 48 h of fermentation. Left (A): Changes in log (CFU/mL) over 48 h during liquid fermentation. Right (B): Changes in log (CFU/g) over 48 h during solid-state fermentation. Fermentations were performed with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. Control represents a negative control that did not receive inoculation. Values are presented as means \pm standard deviation (black bars) from triplicates. Significance from paired t-test is shown as: *, $p < 0.05$, **, $p < 0.01$, ***, $p < 0.001$. ND: not detectable (< 2 log (CFU)).

Figure 10 shows the results of the measured viable counts / CFU from liquid (Figure 10, left (A)) and solid-state fermentation (Figure 10, right (B)) over 48 h (0 h: grey, 48 h: green). The viable count results on the y-axis are shown as log (CFU/mL) for liquid and log (CFU/g) for solid-state, with the x-axis indicating the four different microorganisms and control.

The results from liquid state fermentation (Figure 10, left) showed that all four microorganisms exhibited significant growth over the 48 h fermentation period, whereas the uninoculated control samples exhibited no detectable viable counts at both the 0 h and 48 h timepoints. More specifically, *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 grew from 5.1 to 9.4 log (CFU/mL) after 48 h, representing an increase of 4.3 log units, resulting in the highest total measured viable counts of any of the four microorganisms during liquid fermentation. In contrast, the microorganism that reached the lowest viable counts was *L. plantarum* 2-1, reaching 8.1 log (CFU/mL) after 48 h, corresponding to an increase of 3 log units from 5.1 log (CFU/mL). Furthermore, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 grew from 4.9 to 8.4 log (CFU/mL), corresponding to an increase of 3.5 log units. Lastly, Figure 10 shows that *B. subtilis* var. *natto* grew from 4.1 log (CFU/mL) to

8.8 log (CFU/mL), corresponding to the highest increase of 4.7 log units exhibited by any of the four microorganisms.

Viable counts measured during solid-state fermentation (Figure 10, right) showed that all four microorganisms displayed significant growth over 48 h, except for control samples, where no viable counts were detected. *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 grew from 5.1 to 9.8 log (CFU/g), representing the highest total measured viable counts among the four microorganisms, which corresponds to an increase of 4.7 log units. For the second LAB, *L. plantarum* 2-1, growth was observed from 4.9 to 9.4 log (CFU/g), an increase of 4.5 log units. For *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, growth from 3.8 to 8.9 log (CFU/g) was observed, representing an increase of 5.1 log units, which was the highest exhibited by any of the microorganisms during solid-state fermentation. *B. subtilis* var. *natto* grew from 4.2 to a total viable count of 8.5 log (CFU/g), an increase of 4.3 log units, both values being the lowest among the microorganisms during solid-state fermentation.

Direct comparison between viable counts observed during liquid and solid-state is limited as the two fermentation systems represent two distinct experiments. Furthermore, liquid viable counts are measured in log (CFU/mL) and solid-state measured in log (CFU/g). However, a trend can be observed, as the two LAB strains reach higher viable counts in solid-state fermentation than in liquid fermentation, whereas the opposite was observed for *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, which reach lower viable counts in solid-state fermentation.

4.1.2 pH development during mono-culture fermentations

The pH measured after 48 hours of liquid and solid-state fermentation with the four food-relevant microorganisms as mono-cultures can be seen in Figure 11. The pH of an uninoculated negative control was also measured at 0 h.

Figure 11: pH values measured after 48 h of liquid (left) and solid (right) mono-culture fermentations. Values are presented as means \pm standard deviation (black bars) from triplicates. Fermentations were performed with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. natto. Control represents a negative control that did not receive inoculation. Significance (vs 48 h control) from unpaired (Welch's test) t-test is shown as *: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$, ns: not significant.

Figure 11 displays the pH (y-axis) measured after 48 h of liquid and solid-state fermentation with the project's four microorganisms (x-axis). Two uninoculated controls (0 h: grey, 48 h: green) were employed, representing sampling prior to and after fermentation, which both exhibited a slightly acidic to neutral pH around 6.1-5.9 for liquid fermentation and 6.3-6.4 for solid-state fermentation, showing no significant change in pH of the medium after 48 h.

After 48 h of liquid fermentation (Figure 11, left) the pH of the samples inoculated with the two LAB strains was significantly lower than the 48 h control, with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 and *L. plantarum* 2-1 exhibiting a pH of 4.9 (1 unit lower than 48 h control) and 4.8 (1.1 units lower than 48 h control) respectively, resulting in *L. plantarum* 2-1 showcasing the strongest acidification. In contrast, the samples inoculated with *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and *B. subtilis* var. natto were not significantly different in comparison to the 48 h control, displaying a pH around 6-6.6.

The pH after 48 h of solid-state fermentation (Figure 11, right) was significantly lower for the two samples inoculated with LAB compared to the 48 h control, both resulting in acidification. Inoculation with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 resulted in a pH of 4.8 (1.6 units lower than 48 h

control), whereas *L. plantarum* 2-1 displayed a pH of 4.5 (1.9 units lower than 48 h control), again resulting in *L. plantarum* 2-1 exhibiting the lowest pH. In contrast to liquid fermentation, samples inoculated with *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and *B. subtilis* var. *natto* were significantly different from the 48 h control, both exhibiting a higher pH. For the sample inoculated with *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, the measured pH was 6.9 (0.5 units higher than the 48 h control). *B. subtilis* var. *natto* resulted in the highest measured pH of 8.5, an alkaline value, which corresponds to 2.1 units higher than the 48 h control, and 1.9 units higher than what was observed during liquid fermentation.

4.1.3 Viable counts/CFU of individual strains within co-cultures

The four strains were then deployed in combinations representing co-culture liquid and solid-state fermentations. The measured viable counts at inoculation (0 h) and after 48 h of fermentation for each individual strain within each co-culture combination can be seen in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Changes in viable counts after 48 h fermentations for specific microorganisms within co-culture conditions. Left (A): Liquid fermentation. Right (B): solid-state fermentation. Fermentations were performed with combinations of *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. Control represents a negative control that did not receive inoculation. Values are presented as means \pm standard deviation (black bars) from triplicates, except for *S. c* NCYC 625 0 h during liquid fermentation and *L. p* 2-1 + *B. s* var. *natto* during solid-state fermentation, which were $n = 2$ due to experimental artifacts. Significant growth from 0 h to 48 h is shown with an asterisk; *: $p < 0.05$, **: $p <$

0.01, ***: $p < 0.001$ (paired t-test). Significant difference between co-culture partners at 48 h within the same medium is highlighted with different letters (one-way ANOVA with post hoc Tukey test).

Figure 12 shows the viable counts (log (CFU)) of the individual microorganism species within a certain co-culture combination (x-axis) prior to fermentation (inoculation concentration), shown on the figure as “Name of strain 0 h” and after 48 h of fermentation with different co-culture partners (“Name of species + partner”). Viable count from liquid fermentation is measured as log (CFU/mL) (Figure 12, left (A)), whereas for solid-state fermentation, the values are log (CFU/g) (Figure 12, right (B)). Two timepoint controls were included, one prior to fermentation (0 h) and one after (48 h); both controls exhibited no viable counts in both solid-state and liquid fermentation.

L. fermentum UFLA CH-13 grew significantly in co-culture with both *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. This was seen in both liquid fermentation and solid-state fermentation. During liquid fermentation, *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 grew to 9.2 log (CFU/mL) with *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 as its partner, which was significantly lower than with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* as its partner, where it grew to log 9.3 (CFU/mL). Regarding solid-state fermentation, here *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 grew to 9.2 log (CFU/g) with *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and to 8.7 log (CFU/g) with *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, not showing a significant statistical difference between the two co-cultures after 48 h.

Viable counts related to the growth of *L. plantarum* 2-1 during co-culture fermentations showed that it grew significantly in both its co-culture combinations, a dynamic which was observed both in liquid and solid-state fermentation. In liquid fermentation, it grew to 8.9 and 7.9 log (CFU/mL) with *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, respectively. Here, growth with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* was significantly lower than growth with *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, the difference constituting 1 log unit. In solid-state fermentation, the same pattern was seen where *L. plantarum* 2-1 grew to 9.1 log (CFU/g) with *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and to a significantly lower 7.5 log (CFU/g) with *B. subtilis* var. *natto*.

For *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, growth was seen with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto* during both liquid and solid-state fermentation. Growth during liquid fermentation resulted in viable counts in the range of 7.6 to 8.3 log (CFU/mL) with the three different partners, with only a significant difference being found between the co-culture

with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 vs with *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, where it grew to a lower viable count with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* compared to *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13. In solid-state fermentation, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 grew to 8.7 log (CFU/g) with both LAB species, resulting in no significant difference between the two samples. However, with *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, the viable counts for *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 were significantly lower at 6.8 log (CFU/g).

B. subtilis var. *natto* did not grow in co-culture with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 during liquid fermentation. However, it did grow from 0 h to 48 h in all other samples, regardless of fermentation medium and partner. During liquid fermentation with *L. plantarum* 2-1 and *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, viable counts for *B. subtilis* var. *natto* resulted in 6.7 and 6.9 log (CFU/mL), respectively, with no significant difference being found. Unlike during liquid fermentation, *B. subtilis* var. *natto* showed significant growth in solid-state fermentation with all three co-culture partners after 48 h, including *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13. The viable counts surmounted to 7.7-8.8 (log (CFU/g) with the different partners, with the only co-cultures significantly different at 48 h being with *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 vs with *L. plantarum* 2-1.

4.1.4 pH development during co-culture fermentation

Figure 13: pH values measured after 48 h of liquid (left) and solid (right) co-culture fermentations. Values are presented as means \pm standard deviation (black bars) from triplicates. Fermentations were performed with combinations of *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. Control represents a negative control that

did not receive inoculation. Significance (vs 48 h control) from unpaired (Welch's test) t-test is shown as; *: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$, ns: not significant.

The pH values (y-axis) after 48 h of liquid (Figure 13, left) and solid-state fermentation (Figure 13, right) with different co-cultures (x-axis) are shown in Figure 13. The pH of the two uninoculated timepoint controls (0 h and 48 h) for liquid fermentation was 6.1, and for solid-state fermentation 6.2, thereby resulting in no significant difference between 0 h and 48 h for both, meaning that the pH of uninoculated samples does not change after 48 h.

During liquid fermentation with co-cultures, 4 out of 5 combinations were significantly different compared to the 48 h control, with the only exception being *L. plantarum* 2-1 + *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, showing a pH of 5.6 with a large standard deviation. The co-cultures containing *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 showed acidification and a significantly lower pH with 5.2 (1.1 lower than the 48 h control) and 4.8 (1.3 lower than the 48 h control) with *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, respectively. *L. plantarum* 2-1 + *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 exhibited a pH of 6, while *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 + *B. subtilis* var. *natto* showcased a significantly higher pH of 6.7, an increase of 0.6 compared to the 48 h control.

In contrast to liquid fermentation, all pH values measured after 48 h of solid-state fermentation were higher than the 48 h control and significantly different. All co-cultures containing *B. subtilis* var. *natto* exhibited alkaline pH values around 8.2-8.3, depending on the co-culture partner. The two pairings containing *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and a LAB strain resulted in a neutral pH around 6.9-7.3.

4.2 Assessing the interactions between microbial strains via spot agar assay

To assess the interactions between *L. fermentum* CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, a spot agar assay was deployed. The results of this interaction assay are summarised in Table 1.

Producer↓ Indicator→	<i>S. cerevisiae</i> 625 lawn	<i>L. fermentum</i> UFLA CH-13 Lawn	<i>L. plantarum</i> 2-1 lawn	<i>B. subtilis</i> var. <i>natto</i> lawn
<i>S. cerevisiae</i> 625	-	-	-	-
<i>L. fermentum</i> UFLA CH-13	-	-	+	+
<i>L. plantarum</i> 2-1	-	+	-	+
<i>B. subtilis</i> var. <i>natto</i>	-	-	-	-

Table 1: An overview of spot agar assay testing interaction between *L. fermentum* CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. Observed inhibition zone is marked as “+”, and no observed inhibition zone is marked as “-“. Within the specific interaction, one microorganism functions as an indicator and one as a producer. The table summarizes observations based on triplicates. A spot of sterile media was applied as a negative control. No growth or inhibition zones were observed for negative control spots.

No inhibition zone was observed between the two LAB species and *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, regardless of their roles as producers and indicators (see Appendix 1-2). Moreover, growth of both the LAB species and *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 was observed on the plates, showing that *S. cerevisiae* NCYC, *L. plantarum* 2-1, and *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 (see Appendix 1-2). These observations indicate no antagonistic/inhibitory behaviour between LAB and *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 under the conditions of the assay. Furthermore, no inhibition zone was also not seen between *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and *B. subtilis* var. *natto* (see Appendix 3). This was also the case for *B. subtilis* var. *natto* vs the two LAB species when *B. subtilis* var. *natto* functioned as the producer. However, the growth of the LAB species could not be confirmed as *B. subtilis* var. *natto* showed overgrowth across the entire plate.

Figure 14: Results of spot agar assay between *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 (left) and *L. plantarum* 2-1 (right) as producers vs *B. subtilis* var. *natto* as indicator (lawn). Pictures are examples from triplicates. Small black dots indicate the position of the negative control.

As seen in Table 1 and Figure 14, inhibition zones were observed between *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 and *L. plantarum* 2-1 and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, when the two LAB species functioned

as producers. The inhibition zones appeared as clear halos around the inoculation positions of the LAB species (see Figure 14). At the outer outline of the halo, the growth of *B. subtilis* var. *natto* was observed in the form of a lawn.

Figure 15: Results of spot agar assay between *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 and *L. plantarum* 2-1. Left: *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 as producer and *L. plantarum* 2-1 as indicator (lawn). Right: *L. plantarum* 2-1 as producer and *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 indicator (lawn). Pictures are examples from triplicates. Small black dots indicate the position of the negative control.

As table one indicates, inhibition zones were observed when testing *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 against *L. plantarum* 2-1, regardless of producers/indicator roles (Figure 15). These inhibition zones were much weaker and less clear than those observed between LAB and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*.

4.3 Investigating potential inhibitory mechanisms between LAB strains

With inhibition zones appearing when testing LAB species against each other in a spot agar assay, further exploration of these observations was conducted by testing multiple strains of *L. plantarum* against multiple strains of *L. fermentum*.

4.3.1 Selection of new LAB strains

Two new strains of *L. fermentum* and *L. plantarum* were selected from a phylogenetic tree based on the binary presence and absence of accessory genes.

Figure 16: Phylogenetic tree of *L. fermentum* (left) and *L. plantarum* (right). The tree was based on the binary presence and absence of accessory genes. Red dots indicate new strains selected, and green dots indicate the original used strains.

The phylogenetic tree used for selection can be seen in Figure 16. The four new strains selected were *L. fermentum* 20-8, *L. fermentum* 24h6h2, *L. plantarum* L106, and *L. plantarum* 36h8h. *L. fermentum* 20-8 and *L. plantarum* L106 were chosen as they showed the greatest relative phylogenetic distance to the original strains, which would suggest a greater difference in accessory gene content compared to the original strain. *L. fermentum* 24h6h2 and *L. plantarum* 36h8h1 were chosen for an intermediate phylogenetic position and therefore reflect intermediate differences in accessory gene content between the original strain and the strain furthest in relative phylogenetic distance to the original strain.

4.3.2 Spot agar assay between LAB strains

With newly selected LAB strains, a new spot agar assay was performed. The results of the assay are summarised in Table 2, while examples of inhibition zones observed are shown in Figure 17.

Producer↓ Indicator→	<i>L. plantarum</i> 2-1	<i>L. plantarum</i> L106	<i>L. plantarum</i> 36H8H1
<i>L. fermentum</i> UFLA CH-13	+	-	-
<i>L. fermentum</i> 20-8	+	-	-
<i>L. fermentum</i> 24H6H2	+	-	-

Producer ↓ Indicator →	<i>L. fermentum</i> UFLA CH-13	<i>L. fermentum</i> 20-8	<i>L. fermentum</i> 24H6H2
<i>L. plantarum</i> 2-1	+	+	+
<i>L. plantarum</i> L106	+	+	+
<i>L. plantarum</i> 36H8H1	+	+	+

Table 2: An overview of spot agar assay testing interaction between three strains of *L. fermentum* and three strains of *L. plantarum* 2-1. Observed inhibition zone is marked as “+”, and no observed inhibition zone is marked as “-“. Within the specific interaction, one microorganism functions as an indicator and one as a producer. The table summarizes observations based on triplicates. A spot of sterile media was applied as a negative control. No growth or inhibition zones were observed for negative control spots. No inhibition was noted if: < 0.1 cm between colony outline and lawn.

Table 2 shows that 13 tested interactions during the agar spot assay resulted in inhibition zones (see Figure 17 for examples). When all *L. plantarum* strains acted as producers, inhibitions were observed, while only three instances of inhibition were observed when *L. fermentum* acted as a producer, which, in all cases, were when specifically *L. plantarum* 2-1 was the indicator (lawn).

Figure 17: Examples of inhibition zones observed during agar spot assay testing multiple *L. fermentum* strains against multiple *L. plantarum* strains. The names before “vs” act as a producer (spot) while the name after acts as an indicator (lawn). Three technical replicates of producer strains are shown on the plates, while pictures are examples from triplicates. Small dots indicate the position of the negative control. See Appendix for remaining interactions (Appendix 4). No inhibition was noted if: < 0.1 cm between colony outline and lawn.

The quantification of the observed inhibition zones can be seen in Figure 18. Here, the results show the measured area of the inhibition zone (y-axis) observed during the different interactions (x-axis) over 48 h. Like with table 2, only three instances of inhibition were observed with *L. fermentum* strains acting as producers, where the inhibition zone also can be seen to be not detectable after 48 h for *L. fermentum* 20-8 vs *L. plantarum* 2-1 and *L. fermentum* 24h6h2 vs *L. plantarum* 2-1. Regarding the interaction between *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 and *L. plantarum* 2-1, where *L. fermentum* functions as a producer, an inhibition zone around 0.5 cm² after both 24 h and 48 h was observed.

Figure 18: Size of inhibition zones (cm²) formed during spot agar assay with strains *L. fermentum* and *L. plantarum*. The upper part shows strains of *L. fermentum* as producers and strains of *L. plantarum* as indicators (lawn). The lower part shows strains of *L. plantarum* as producers and strains of *L. fermentum* as indicators (lawn). Red bars indicate values measured after 24 h, while blue indicates measurements after 48 h. No bars indicate non-detectable inhibition zones. Values are shown as means ± standard deviation (black bars) from triplicates.

When *L. plantarum* strains acted as producers, measurable inhibition zones for all tested interactions after both 24 h and 48 h were observed. Trends can be seen when comparing the different *L. plantarum* strains, as *L. plantarum* 36h8h1 and *L. plantarum* L106, create inhibition zones around 0.5-1 cm², while all inhibition zones created by *L. plantarum* 2-1 were < 0.5 cm².

4.3.3 Abundance of bacteriocin-related genes in bacterial genomes

After seeing the inhibition zones formed during the agar spot assay between *L. fermentum* and *L. plantarum* a bioinformatical screening of the annotated genomes of the six tested strains was performed. The purpose of the screening was to assess the abundance and presence of bacteriocin-related genes. The results of said screening can be seen in Figure 19.

Figure 19: The abundance of bacteriocin-related genes in the annotated genomes of six different LAB strains. Specific annotations found in the genome are shown along the x-axis, while the different strains are shown on the y-axis. Numbers indicate the abundance of specific annotations.

Figure 19 shows that for the three tested *L. fermentum* strains, no annotations related to bacteriocins or bacteriocin immunity were found. For the three *L. plantarum* strains tested, all showed they contained the presence of annotations related to bacteriocins and bacteriocin immunity. A high abundance of bacteriocin immunity annotated genes was found in all three strains, with abundances ranging between 8 and 10. Regarding specific bacteriocin annotations, it can be seen that the three strains vary in their content, with all strains at least containing two annotated genes related to specific bacteriocins. *L. plantarum* L106 and *L. plantarum* 36h8h1 contained 2 and 5 annotations related to plantarcins, while also containing a gene annotation related to lactococin-G. The screening of *L. plantarum* 2-1's genome also showed the presence of the lactococin-G related annotation, while as the only strain also showing the presence of a mesentericin related gene.

4.3.4 Well diffusion assay

After showing the presence of multiple different genes related to bacteriocins in the genomes of the LAB strains, a well diffusion assay using proteinase K was deployed to detect potential bacteriocin activity between *L. plantarum* and *L. fermentum* strains. The results of the well diffusion assay are exemplified in Figure 20.

L. plantarum 36h8h1 as lawn with wells containing supernatant from *L. fermentum* strains

L. fermentum 20-8 as lawn with wells containing supernatant from *L. plantarum* strains

Figure 20: Example of plates from well diffusion assay using *L. plantarum* 36h8h1 as indicator (lawn) and wells with supernatant from different *L. fermentum* strains (left). *L. fermentum* 20-8 as an indicator (lawn) and wells with supernatant from different *L. fermentum* strains (left). The different well labels indicate: Strain name, S: supernatant, S.: supernatant diluted 50%, K: supernatant + Proteinase K, NC: Negative control. The images show results from one biological replicate.

No inhibition zones around any wells were observed after performing the well diffusion. This was regardless of supernatant dilution, species, and the addition of proteinase K.

4.4 Impact of fermentation on trypsin inhibitor activity in faba beans

After performing liquid and solid-state fermentations with mono-cultures and co-cultures, the next objective was to test the level of trypsin inhibitor activity in fermented sample to see if fermentation with the project's microorganisms individually and in combinations had the ability to reduce the activity of trypsin inhibitors' ability to inhibit trypsin. This was carried out using a trypsin inhibitor assay.

4.4.1 Trypsin units inhibited in mono-culture fermentation

Figure 21: TUI/mg values measured on samples from 48 h liquid (left) and solid-state (right) mono-culture fermentations. Values are presented as means \pm standard deviation (black bars) from triplicates. Fermentations were performed with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. Control represents a negative control that did not receive inoculation. Significance (vs 48 h control) from unpaired (Welch's test) t-test is shown as *: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$, ns: not significant.

Results from the trypsin inhibitor assay can be seen in Figure 21. The figure displays the trypsin units inhibited represented as TUI/mg (y-axis) in each sample (x-axis). Two uninoculated control samples are included, corresponding to sampling prior to and after fermentation (0 h: grey, 48 h: green).

In liquid fermentation, no significant difference in TUI/mg was observed between the uninoculated controls after 48 h, having observed TUI/mg levels around 6. Furthermore, no inoculated samples from liquid fermentation (Figure 21, left) were significantly different in their concentration of TUI/mg compared to the 48 h control. Samples inoculated with LAB and *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 exhibited TUI/mg in the range of 6.2-6.6. The liquid fermentation sample inoculated with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* was the lowest, resulting in 4.9 TUI/mg, however not statistically different from the 48 h control.

Results from solid-state fermentation (Figure 21, right) showcased the same pattern as seen in liquid fermentation. The control samples were not significantly different from each other, and samples inoculated with LAB and *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 displayed TUI/mg values not significantly different from the 48 h control, with TUI/mg values in the range of 5.9-7.1.

However, the sample inoculated with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* exhibited a significantly lower concentration of 2.4 TUI/mg, which is a reduction of around 60% compared to the 48 h control.

4.4.2 Trypsin units inhibited in co-culture solid-state fermentation

With the only mono-culture showing a significant reduction in TUI/mg being *B. subtilis* var. *natto* (60%) during solid-state fermentation, the trypsin inhibitor assay was only performed on co-culture samples from solid-state fermentations. This was done to assess if the reduction seen fermenting with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* as a mono-culture would also persist in co-cultures.

Figure 22: TUI/mg values measured on samples from solid-state co-culture fermentations. Values are presented as means \pm standard deviation (black bars) from triplicates. Fermentations were performed with combinations of *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. Control represents a negative control that did not receive inoculation. Significance (vs 48 h control) from unpaired (Welch's test) t-test is shown as: *: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$, ns: not significant.

Figure 22 shows the TUI/mg (y-axis) results in solid-state fermentation samples using different co-cultures (x-axis). No significant difference was found between the 0 h control and 48 h, showcasing again that the TUI/mg of uninoculated samples does not change after 48 h. Furthermore, the results showed that the samples containing *B. subtilis* var. *natto* were significantly lower compared to the 48 h control. Combinations containing *B. subtilis* var. *natto* and either *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 or *L. plantarum* 2-1 exhibited a TUI/mg around 2.6-3.1, with the *B. subtilis* var. *natto* + *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 sample resulting in 3.9 TUI/mg. Specifically, co-culture samples containing *B. subtilis* var. *natto* exhibited a reduction of TUI/mg in the range of 43.5 to 62.3 % depending on the specific co-culture partner, with *B.*

subtilis var. *natto* + *L. plantarum* 2-1 reducing the TUI/mg the most with 62.3 %, a change from 6.9 to 2.6 TUI/mg being the largest reduction among the three significant co-cultures.

4.4.3 Assessing the extracellular proteolytic potential of LAB and *B. subtilis* var. *natto* genomically

After showcasing that fermentation samples with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* were significantly lower compared to the control, a bioinformatic screening was performed to estimate the extracellular proteolytic potential based on the abundance of domains associated with protein families associated with extracellular proteases (see 3.6.3).

Protein family	<i>B. subtilis</i> var. <i>natto</i>	<i>L. plantarum</i> 2-1	<i>L. fermentum</i> UFLA CH-13
Peptidase_S8	7	1	0
Peptidase_M4	1	0	0
Total	8	1	0

Table 3: Table showing the abundance of protein sequences containing a domain assigned to a specific protein family found in the annotated genomes of *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, *L. plantarum* 2-1, and *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13. Protein families selected are known to contain extracellular proteases (Harwood & Kikuchi, 2022; M. Liu et al., 2010)

Table 3 shows that the three annotated genomes of the bacteria differ in their content of proteins containing domains assigned to the selected protein families. Table 3 shows that in total, *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, *L. fermentum* CH-13, and *L. plantarum* 2-1 contain 8, 1, and 0 proteins containing domains assigned to the protein families selected for association with extracellular proteases of the three bacteria. Regarding protein families S8 and M4, Table 3 shows that for *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, 8 matches were found in the genome, whereas the two LAB strains only contained 1 match combined. Specifically for protein sequences containing a domain that is linked to the S8 protein family, it was seen that *B. subtilis* var. *natto* contained seven matches, while *L. plantarum* 2-1 contained 1.

query name	accession	--- full sequence ---			--- best 1 domain ---			description of target
		E-value	score	bias	E-value	score	bias	
Peptidase_S8	PF00082.25	9.4e-80	265.9	9.2	1.6e-79	265.2	9.2	serine protease Vpr
Peptidase_S8	PF00082.25	8.3e-69	230.0	0.8	1e-68	229.7	0.8	serine protease Isp
Peptidase_S8	PF00082.25	1.7e-66	222.4	15.7	2.5e-66	221.8	15.7	subtilisin AprE
Peptidase_S8	PF00082.25	2.8e-62	208.6	0.4	3.7e-62	208.2	0.4	serine protease AprX
Peptidase_S8	PF00082.25	7e-60	200.7	3.9	7e-60	200.7	3.9	cell wall-associated protease WprA
Peptidase_S8	PF00082.25	8.4e-60	200.4	9.8	1.7e-59	199.4	9.8	minor protease Epr
Peptidase_S8	PF00082.25	3e-57	192.1	0.9	9.4e-57	190.4	0.9	bacillopeptidase F

Figure 23: Further description of the matches found in *B. subtilis* var. *natto* belonging to the peptidase S8 protein family

Figure 23 shows the 7 matches found within the annotated genome of *B. subtilis* var. *natto* that contained a domain assigned to protein family “Peptidase S8”, a family known to contain extracellular proteases. For each match, E-value, bit-score, and bias are shown for the whole sequence and the best single domain. All matches show very significant e-values and high bit scores, underlining the high probability that the matches’ assignment to the peptidase S8 family is correct. The specific protein names of seven matches can be seen under “description of target”, which uses the assigned annotation given in the genome.

4.5 Volatile organic compound profiles of solid-state fermented faba beans

GC-MS was performed to investigate the potential of the project’s four different microorganisms’ ability to change the aroma/VOC profile of faba beans through solid-state fermentation. Both mono-cultures and co-cultures samples from the completed solid-state fermentations were analysed.

4.5.1 Overall changes to the VOC composition

Figure 24: The percentage distribution of major VOC classes in faba beans after 48 h of solid-state fermentation. Fermentation was performed with mono-culture and co-cultures consisting of: *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. Uninoculated controls prior to and (0 h) and after sampling (48 h) are also included. Percentages are based on means from triplicates. “Others” include furans, terpenes, and ethers. N-compounds: nitrogen-containing compounds (e.g., pyrazines, pyridines, and pyrimidines).

Figure 24 shows that the percentages of major volatile classes making up the composition of VOC change majorly depending on sample conditions. The 0 h control shows that the VOC profile of soaked dehulled whole faba beans is dominated by aldehydes (71.2 %), with the second most abundant class being alcohols (20.9 %). The remaining composition is comprised of ketones (5.6 %), others (1.3 %), acids (0.8 %), N-compounds (0.2 %), and esters (0.1 %). After 48 h, the uninoculated control shows an almost identical composition to the 0 h control, suggesting that simply time does not affect the VOC profile. The biggest difference between the two controls was seen regarding aldehydes, which went up by 3.1 % in the 48 h control compared to the 0 h control.

Figure 24 shows that the VOC profile after 48 h changes drastically when inoculated with the project’s four different microorganisms. This change occurred regardless of species and regardless of whether the sample was fermented with mono-cultures or co-cultures. The biggest

difference between the controls and the inoculated samples can be seen in the percentage of aldehydes. Inoculated samples show aldehyde levels in the range of 18.1-3.0 %, corresponding to a reduction in the range of 71.3-56.2 % compared to the 48 h control. The second biggest difference when comparing the control to inoculated samples is the increase in ketones, which accounted for 5.6-6.9 % in control samples, but increased to 22.8-52.9 % in inoculated samples.

Samples fermented with the two LAB species: *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 and *L. plantarum* 2-1 as mono-cultures resulted in a higher percentage of acids and esters compared to the control samples and fermentation samples where *B. subtilis* var. natto and *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 were present. Specifically, the VOC composition of mono-culture fermentation with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 and *L. plantarum* 2-1 showed acids accounting for 10.2 % and 7.5 %, respectively. Secondly, mono-culture fermentation with LAB species showed esters accounting for 1.6-1.3 %, which was different from all other samples, where they accounted for < 0.5 %.

Fermentation samples with *B. subtilis* var. natto showed almost identical VOC composition regardless of being as a mono-culture or a co-culture. These samples were characterized by their large proportions of ketones, like the other inoculated samples. However, fermentation samples with *B. subtilis* var. natto were unique in their higher percentage of nitrogen-containing compounds (N-compounds), accounting for 15.6-23.0 % depending on sample condition, with the mono-culture showing the highest percentage (23.0 %). In contrast, N-compounds accounted < 1 % in all other samples.

VOC composition of samples containing *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 was mainly (apart from co-culture with *B. subtilis* var. natto) characterized by their higher proportions of alcohols compared to other samples. The highest proportion of alcohols of all samples analysed was seen in mono-culture fermentation with *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, accounting for 66.5 % of the overall composition.

4.5.2 Principal component analysis

Figure 25: Principal component analysis (PCA) of VOC profiles from completed mono- and co-culture solid-state fermentation samples. VOC profiles are based on log-transformed normalized concentrations for each compound. Left: score plot showing the separation of samples based on VOC profiles/composition, with each sample being coloured distinctly and each point representing a biological replicate. Labels above point indicate sample name/conditions. Right: loading plot showing each individual VOC's contribution to separation with regard to PC1 and PC2. Labels above point indicate compound name and each point is coloured according to compound class. "Others" include furans, terpenes, and ethers. N-compounds: nitrogen-containing compounds (e.g., pyrazines, pyridines, and pyrimidines).

Figure 25 shows the results of a PCA of solid-state fermentation samples based on VOC composition. The analysis shows that PC1 and PC2 explain 37.7 and 20.1% (57.8 % combined) of total variance, respectively. The score plot shows clear clustering of the different fermentation samples based on VOC composition. The control samples cluster visibly together on positive PC1 and negative PC2, with clear separations from samples inoculated with microorganisms. This can be seen as samples containing microorganisms either cluster negatively along PC1 and negatively along PC2, or positively along PC2 and at intermediate PC1 values. This stands in contrast to the pattern seen for the control samples, which suggests a major difference in VOC composition between control and fermented (inoculated) samples. Furthermore, the clustering of the control samples and their separation from the other samples

is mainly associated with aldehydes, such as butanal and hexanal, and alcohols such as butanol and pentanol. This can be seen as the loading plot shows a clustering pattern for these compounds corresponding to the clustering pattern seen for the control samples on the score plot. These PCA placements suggest that aldehydes in general and some specific ones like hexanal contribute considerably to the VOC profile of dehulled soaked faba beans, which received no inoculation and therefore did not undergo fermentation.

Among the samples inoculated with microorganisms, clear clustering is observed, with two cluster patterns appearing. One grouping of samples all containing *B. subtilis* var. *natto* as either mono-culture or as a participant in co-cultures can be seen clustering at negatively PC1 and PC2 values. This cluster and its separation can be seen to be associated with N-compounds such as pyrimidine-4-methyl and pyrazine-trimethyl, as these compounds form a corresponding cluster/separation pattern on the loading plot. This suggests that N-compounds contribute substantially to the VOC profile of samples fermented with *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. Certain alcohol compounds, such as 2-heptanol-6-methyl and 4-methyl-2-hexanol, on the loading plot can also be seen to match the PCA position of the samples containing *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, suggesting an association between these compounds and the VOC profile of these samples. Furthermore, ketones also appear to be relevant for this cluster's separation, with 2-decanone and 3-octanone being examples of compounds tightly positioned on the loading plot, corresponding to *B. subtilis* var. *natto* containing samples on the score plot.

The second cluster pattern among inoculated samples can be seen forming at the top of the score plot at positive PC2 values. The samples at this position contain *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, and *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, forming a clear separation from samples containing *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. The biological replicates of these samples also appear to be clustering more tightly, separating samples based on specific species and also whether they are mono-cultures or co-cultures. This suggests consistency among the biological replicates and the samples' VOC profile. Specific compounds shown on the loading plot that correspond and thereby associate with the VOC profile of this cluster include acetoin, acetic acid, 2-3 butanedione, phenylethyl-alcohol, ethyl-acetate, and 1-butanol-3-methyl-acetate. Specifically, the score plot shows that *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 mono-cultures clustering tight at the top of the positive PC2 axis, which on the loading plot corresponds to specific compounds such as the ketone acetoin and alcohols such as 1-butanol-3-methyl and 3-buten-1-ol-3-methyl. Two esters, ethyl-acetate and 1-butanol-3-methyl-acetate, appear in this region

on the loading plot, holding positions corresponding to samples containing *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and *L. plantarum* 2-1 as mono-cultures. Furthermore, the loading plot shows acetic acid at a position corresponding to samples on the score plot containing *L. plantarum* 2-1 as either mono-culture or a participant in co-culture with *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625.

4.5.3 The impact of solid-state fermentation on “beany” off-flavor aldehydes

Figure 26: The normalized concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) of six different “beany” off-flavor aldehydes (2-Octenal (e), 3-Methyl-butanal, Benzaldehyde, Hexanal, Nonanal, and Pentanal) after 48 h solid-state fermentation. Fermentation was done with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. Control represents a negative control that did not receive inoculation. Values are shown as means \pm standard deviation (black bars) from triplicates. Different letters indicate a significant difference between samples (one-way ANOVA + Tukey’s post hoc test).

Figure 26 shows the normalised concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) (y-axis) of six different aldehydes characterised as contributors to “beany” off-flavor in legumes (Fischer et al., 2022) after 48 h of solid-state fermentation with mono-cultures and co-cultures of *L. fermentum* CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*.

Firstly, it can be seen from the controls sample, which did not receive any inoculation, that the normalised concentrations did not change significantly between 0 h and 48 h in four (2-Octenal (E), 3-Methyl-butanal, benzaldehyde, and nonanal) out of six compounds shown. However, for

hexanal and pentanal, the normalised concentration did reduce significantly after 48 h from 7554.6 to 4536.4 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) and from 428.7 to 310.5 regarding hexanal and pentanal respectively. These results show that time is a factor for the concentration of some compounds, but not for all.

For hexanal, pentanal, and 2-Octenal (E) the figure shows that samples which underwent solid-state fermentation with mono-cultures and co-cultures reduced the normalised concentration significantly regardless of species. This significant reduction was seen both when comparing to the 0 h control and the 48 h control. Specifically, hexanal, which had a concentration of 4536.4 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) after 48 h, was reduced to levels around 31.7-276.7 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) in samples inoculated with microorganisms. Between the different mono-culture and co-culture samples, there were no significant differences. However, these results indicate that solid-state fermentation has a significant impact on the concentration of hexanal, pentanal, and 2-octenal.

Regarding the concentration of 3-methyl-butanal, it can be seen that three samples are significantly different: *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, *B. subtilis* var. *natto* + *L. plantarum* 2-1, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto* + *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, which all showed significantly higher concentration compared to both the 0 h control and 48 h control (except *B. subtilis* var. *natto* + *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, which was only significantly higher than 0 h control).

For benzaldehyde, all inoculated samples showed significantly reduced levels of concentration compared to the 0 h control, except for samples containing *B. subtilis* var. *natto* or the sample with *L. plantarum* 2-1 as a mono-culture. All other samples showed no significant differences in the concentration levels.

Lastly, for nonanal, no samples displayed significant differences in normalised concentrations.

4.6 Visualizing the structural impact of solid-state fermentation on faba beans using confocal microscopy

To visualize the structural effects of solid-state fermentation on faba beans, a methodology was evaluated to determine whether different plant cell components could be visualized in faba beans. All solid-state fermentation mono-culture samples, containing *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, and control samples prior

to (0 h) and after fermentation (48 h) were stained with four staining conditions: no stain (autofluorescence), Calcofluor White, BODIPY, and Rhodamine B. Each stain was used to visualize a specific component within the plant cell, with Calcofluor White staining cellulose and chitin, BODIPY staining lipid droplets, and Rhodamine B staining proteins.

Images were obtained from the 0 h control, 48 h control, and mono-culture fermentations with the four microbial strains. The images from 48 h control samples were used to optimize microscopy settings for clearest visualization, and those settings then served as a reference for all other images. The images of the 48 h control can be seen in Figure 27, with images obtained from the remaining samples being shown in the appendix (see Appendix 5-9)

Figure 27: Confocal microscopy images of 48 h control samples from solid-state fermentation. Letters indicate the different staining conditions. A: No stain; B: Calcofluor White; C: BODIPY; D: Rhodamine B. Images include a scale bar of 100 μm , providing spatial reference for observed plant cell structures

Figure 27 shows images of uninoculated solid-state fermentation samples with the four different staining conditions previously described. Furthermore, the figure shows that different

staining conditions produce distinct fluorescence patterns within the cellular matrix. Firstly, without staining (A), weak autofluorescence still appeared as small oval shapes representing the autofluorescence components within the sample matrix. Secondly, staining with Calcofluor White (B) produced an image where the fluorescent pattern appeared as thin blue lines outlining the autofluorescent oval shapes seen in (A). This pattern and Calcofluor White's known binding affinity to cellulose suggest that what is seen is cell-wall structures surrounding individual plant cells. Thirdly, the fluorescent pattern seen when staining with BODIPY (C) appeared as green little dots in clusters surrounding and in between the autofluorescent oval shapes seen in (A). Lastly, staining with Rhodamine B (D) produced the most distinct image compared to no staining (A). The image shows red fluorescence throughout the whole sample matrix, with the fluorescence being noticeably stronger within structures corresponding to the shape of plant cells. Within these structures, the red fluorescence surrounds the oval-shaped structures seen in all the other images, with the oval-shaped structures themselves showing a clearer blue fluorescence and a more defined shape and outline.

5. Discussion

5.1 Growth and pH dynamics of food-relevant microorganisms during faba bean fermentation

One of the project's objectives was to assess the capacity of four food-relevant microorganisms to grow during the fermentation of faba beans as both mono-cultures and co-cultures. Therefore, liquid and solid-state fermentation of faba beans was conducted, which revealed that as mono-cultures, *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto* all were able to grow during fermentation of faba beans in both fermentation media. This was seen as all mono-cultures increased significantly in terms of log (CFU/mL) during liquid fermentation and log (CFU/g) during solid-state fermentation. The observed ability of these microorganisms to grow during faba bean fermentation is consistent with current literature, as all four species have been shown to grow in a variety of legume-based matrices (Adeyemo & Onilude, 2013; Barampama & Simard, 1994; Chi & Cho, 2016; Qi et al., 2024). Specifically, regarding growth during liquid fermentation, the findings in (Larsen et al., 2026) demonstrated similar results, showing that another strain of *L. fermentum* (NSB2) and *B. subtilis* var. *natto* were able to reach viable counts of ~ 8-8.8 log (CFU/mL)

after 48 h of fermentation utilizing an 8 % (w/v) suspension of faba bean concentrate in distilled water. Adding to this, *B. subtilis* var. *natto* is a microorganism specifically used to ferment whole legumes, as it is inoculated into cooked soybeans in the process of making natto (Wang et al., 2023). Furthermore, the ability of LAB to grow and ferment faba bean would also be expected, as a variety of LAB strains have been isolated from spontaneously fermented faba bean flour and shown to have the ability to metabolize a variety of carbohydrates (Verni et al., 2017). Lastly, the fermentative capacity and growth of *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 are also backed up by previously reported results, as the species has been used in multiple studies working with solid-state fermentation of a legume matrix (Chi & Cho, 2016; Hassaan et al., 2015).

After 48 h, pH measurements showed that mono-culture fermentation with both *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 and *L. plantarum* 2-1 significantly reduced the pH regardless of the fermentation medium. This can be explained by the metabolism of LAB, which produces organic acids while fermenting carbohydrates. These organic acids diffuse throughout the food matrix, thereby lowering the pH of the surrounding environment (Punia Bangar et al., 2022). Furthermore, the ability of LAB to decrease pH within a food matrix has been well demonstrated (Cichońska & Ziarno, 2021). (Larsen et al., 2026) demonstrated that *L. fermentum* (NSB2) led to acidification during fermentation of a liquid faba bean medium. Additionally, this has also been shown in solid-state fermentation of other legumes, such as lupins (Ayyash et al., 2019). Here, 48 h of solid-state fermentation with *L. plantarum* DSM and *L. plantarum* KX881779 resulted in a pH of 3.5 and 3.6, respectively (Ayyash et al., 2019).

In contrast, the solid-state fermentation with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* as a mono-culture significantly alkalized the medium, which was not seen in liquid fermentation. The alkalization seen during solid-state fermentation is likely explained by the production of ammonia during protein degradation, which is a key characteristic of natto fermentation. As mentioned in the introduction, *B. subtilis* possesses high proteolytic capacity with multiple extracellular and intracellular proteases. These proteases degrade proteins, releasing free amino acids, which, when metabolised, release ammonia (Rocchi et al., 2024; Wu, 2009). When ammonia is released and reacts with water, hydroxide ions are produced, raising the pH (alkalinity) (Sanger & Danner, 2010). The alkalization during fermentation of legumes using *B. subtilis* strains has been reported in multiple studies. (Rocchi et al., 2024) showed that fermentation of red lentils, green peas, chickpeas, and lupins with different *B. subtilis* strains lead to a significant increase in pH compared to the control. Furthermore, it was also shown

that the fermentation of these legumes led to a significant increase in the concentration of ammonia compared to the control. Additionally, (Pradhananga, 2019; Wei et al., 2001) also showed a significant increase in pH during *natto* fermentation. With this in mind, the results shown in this project regarding faba beans replicate the characteristics of *natto* fermentation performed on different legumes in various studies.

Results from the co-culture fermentation showed that *L. fermentum* UFLA, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto* all showed significant growth in both fermentation media, with the exception of *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, which was not detectable after 48 h during co-culture fermentation with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13. This observation indicates inhibition of *B. subtilis* var. *natto* and could be explained by this co-culture sample's corresponding pH value, which was measured to be 4.8 after 48 h. If this decrease in pH is caused by the production of organic acids, it could potentially explain why *B. subtilis* var. *natto* was not detected, as organic acids have been shown to possess antimicrobial properties. The inhibitory mechanism of organic acids is often seen through their ability to cross the cell membrane in their undissociated forms and cause an accumulation of protons that results in a reduction of the intracellular pH. The cell then maintains a neutral pH and consumes ATP in order to actively pump out the protons, ultimately leading to a depletion of the cell (Punia Bangar et al., 2022; Ricke, 2003). Furthermore, it has been shown that *B. subtilis* is inhibited by various organic acids measured using minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs), which also showed that MICs for different organic acids were significantly lower for *B. subtilis* compared to *L. fermentum* and *L. plantarum* (Hsiao & Siebert, 1999).

When connecting this inhibition to the observed growth of *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 during its co-culture with *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 reached 9.3 log (CFU/mL), which was significantly higher than with *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and even though direct comparison with mono-culture growth is limited, a similar viable count of 9.4 log (CFU/mL) after 48 h was observed. This could imply that the interaction may resemble amensalism, which is characterised as an interaction where one microorganism is inhibited, and one remains unaffected (W. Liu et al., 2025).

One reason why this observation was seen during co-culture with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 but not *L. plantarum* 2-1 could be due to differences in the metabolic profile of the two LAB species. Although *L. plantarum* is classified as a facultative heterofermentative, it primarily

utilizes the homofermentative pathway, resulting in primarily lactic acid production, whereas the obligate heterofermentative *L. fermentum* could produce different organic acids (Gänzle, 2015). To this point, (Hsiao & Siebert, 1999) showed that MIC for *B. subtilis* was different when comparing the inhibitory effect of different types of organic acids. For instance, the MIC when testing lactic acid was 8.32 g/L, which was higher than when utilizing acetic acid, benzoic acid, and butyric acid, resulting in MIC values of 0.105 g/L, 0.192 g/L, and 0.096 g/L, respectively.

Solid-state fermentation with co-cultures showed that all samples containing *B. subtilis* var. *natto* had significantly higher pH compared to the control, reflecting the previously described characteristic alkalization seen during natto fermentation. On the other hand, this was not the case during co-culture liquid fermentations, with only *B. subtilis* var. *natto* + *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 showing significantly higher pH, with samples containing *B. subtilis* + LAB either reducing or maintaining the same pH compared to the control. This shows that in solid-state fermentation, the presence of LAB in co-cultures with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* is not able to reduce the pH of the medium as they did during mono-culture solid-state/liquid fermentation or co-culture liquid fermentations. This trend could indicate that the environmental conditions of the two fermentation media play a significant role when it comes to the behaviour/ecology of *B. subtilis* var. *natto*.

As the mono-culture and co-culture fermentations were conducted as separate experiments due to time constraints, direct comparison of growth outcomes between them is heavily limited. Ultimately, this allows for poor characterization of the different interactions within co-cultures compared to the microorganisms undergoing fermentation individually. Therefore, in future studies or if more time were available, a different experimental setup would be beneficial to implement. Ideally, the setup should be constructed in such a way that both the mono-cultures and the co-cultures are included in the same experiment. This would allow for optimal comparison, because this would ensure the same viable counts at inoculation (0 h) and the same experimental conditions across biological replicates for both mono-cultures and co-cultures. As a result, the viable count after 48 h for the mono-culture could be directly compared to the viable counts after 48 h with different co-culture partners, which would better reveal synergistic or antagonistic/inhibitory interactions.

5.2 Further assessments of interactions between food-relevant microorganisms

An agar spot assay was performed with the intention of potentially providing insights into the relationships/interactions between the microorganisms used for the different fermentations. The agar spot assay revealed no inhibition between the two LAB strains and *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625. This reflects the growth outcomes seen during co-culture experiments, where in all co-cultures with *L. plantarum* 2-1 + *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 or *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 + *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, regardless of fermentation medium, growth of both microorganisms was observed. These results were expected as the pairing between LAB and *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 is frequently seen in food fermentation (Cheng et al., 2025), exemplified by the mutualistic relationship seen during sourdough fermentation (Gobbetti & Corsetti, 1997).

One interaction that was also reflected in the agar spot assay and in the co-culture fermentation was the inhibitory interaction between *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. This inhibitory effect seen in both setups could potentially make *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 a candidate regarding food safety and bioprotective culture against *Bacillus* species, as they are naturally found in plant materials and can cause both foodborne diseases and spoilage (Skriver et al., 2026). However, much more investigation is needed to reach a conclusive evaluation.

However, in the agar spot assay, *L. plantarum* 2-1 was shown to inhibit *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, which does not occur during co-culture fermentation with the microorganism as a partner to *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. One explanation could lie in the design of the assay, as the producers grow for an extended period of time before the indicator microorganisms are introduced. This fact allows for an establishment period for the microorganism acting as a producer. In this period, the microorganism is unchallenged in its ability to modulate the environment, which in the context of LAB would be relevant regarding the acidification of the surrounding area of the inoculation spot. In the unchallenged period, *L. plantarum* 2-1 is allowed to reduce the pH of the surrounding environment without competition, but in the fermentation setting, both microorganisms are inoculated at the same time, allowing for both microorganisms to produce metabolites into the media, and as described *B. subtilis* var. *natto* causes alkalization, whereas *L. plantarum* 2-1 causes acidification, meaning opposite effects on the pH. This is further

supported by the measured pH of the liquid co-culture containing the microorganisms after 48 h, which was not significantly different from the control.

The results showing that LAB has the ability to inhibit the growth of *Bacillus* are in line with studies found in the literature. Both (Røssland et al., 2003) and (Yang et al., 2008) showed LAB was able to inhibit the growth of *B. cereus* during fermentation. Specifically, (Røssland et al., 2003) showed during skimmed milk fermentation that co-culture with *L. plantarum* 2741 and *B. subtilis* NVH 45 resulted in <1 log (CFU/mL) for *B. cereus* after 48 h fermentation, with the corresponding pH being 4.7. This study also tested a *L. fermentum* strain, which, however, did not inhibit the *Bacillus* as effectively as the *L. plantarum* strain, as *B. cereus* grew to 7.86 log (CFU/mL) in co-culture with *L. fermentum* 99 after 48 h. These results show the opposite of what was shown during this project's liquid fermentation with co-cultures, as *L. plantarum* 2-1 was not able to inhibit *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, but *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 was. This could be explained by the differences in specific LAB strains used, fermentation medium, and *Bacillus* species.

Another presumptively inhibitory interaction was seen during the agar spot assay, where inhibition zones between *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 and *L. plantarum* 2-1 were observed, which was further confirmed to also occur when testing two different *L. plantarum* strains against two different *L. fermentum* strains. On one hand, this inhibition was considered unlikely to be a result of low pH or the production of organic acids, as both strains produce these and are adapted to tolerate acidic environments (Papadimitriou et al., 2016). This is supported by the findings (Hsiao & Siebert, 1999), which showed that both a strain of *L. plantarum* and a strain of *L. fermentum* had high and similar MICs with regard to lactic acid and acetic acid. However, on the other hand, (Hsiao & Siebert, 1999) also showed that both strains had about ~10x lower MICs regarding benzoic and caprylic acid compared to the other organic acids. Therefore, the inhibition seen could potentially be caused by differences in organic acid production profiles, meaning that potentially the tested *L. plantarum* strains produce a type of organic acid to which *L. fermentum* is susceptible. Supporting this possibility, it has been shown in (Mao et al., 2020) that an *L. plantarum* strain possesses several antibacterial substances, including propionic acid and caprylic acid. To further test this, future studies would need to characterise the exact metabolic profile of the strains.

Another possible cause for the inhibition zones observed between the two LAB species was thought to potentially be the result of bacteriocins, which would resemble interference competition (Stubbendieck & Straight, 2016). This was thought, as argued in (Eijsink et al., 2002), to be possible as bacteriocins can have a narrow inhibitory spectrum primarily aimed at competitors within the same ecological niche, which in our case would be an acidic environment, where LAB compete against other LAB. Moreover, LAB are known producers of bacteriocins (Xu et al., 2025), and specifically for *L. plantarum*, studies have shown the distribution (Choi et al., 2021) of bacteriocin genes across multiple different strains. Furthermore, this was also shown by this project's screening of the *L. plantarum* strains' annotated genomes (Figure 19). With all this in mind, a well diffusion was therefore deployed utilizing cell-free supernatant (CFS) and proteinase K to investigate potential bacteriocin activity between strains of *L. plantarum* and *L. fermentum*. The results from the well diffusion showed no inhibition zones at all, regardless of using CFS or CFS + proteinase K, suggesting that the inhibition zones seen in the agar spot assay may not have been caused by compounds excreted into CFS, which would include bacteriocins. These results, however, do not conclusively confirm that bacteriocin activity does not occur between the two species, as the bacteriocin production could potentially be dependent on a factor not replicated in the deployed experimental setup. Furthermore, the interpretation of the observed results is limited and would become more robust with more biological and technical replicates, as it would further enhance the reproducibility of the results

Firstly, one potential reason why bacteriocins might not be present in the CFS used in the well diffusion assay could be due to too low cell density during incubation, as the production of bacteriocins can be cell density-dependent (Eijsink et al., 2002), with the production being heavily linked to the quorum-sensing system. This means that for production of bacteriocins to occur, a certain external threshold regarding autoinducers must be achieved (Eijsink et al., 2002). Therefore, to ensure that this threshold and the required cell densities are reached, future studies could increase the incubation period to span over 24-72 h. Furthermore, this could also potentially explain why inhibition zones occurred in agar spot assay, as the inoculation of the producers is confined to a small area on the plate with a subsequent incubation, leading to an area of high cell-density compared to when producers are grown in liquid media with the intention of harvesting the CFS. Further support for this methodology optimization is also backed up by maximum bacteriocin production being linked to the stationary phase, which was

shown in both (Malheiros et al., 2015) and (Castro et al., 2011), where the highest production of bacteriocins by different species/strains of LAB was observed in the stationary phase.

Lastly, findings in (W. He et al., 2025) showed that a co-culture setup with *L. fermentum* and *L. plantarum* enhanced the production of bacteriocins. This was shown through an inhibitory activity test, where the observed inhibition zones were significantly larger for supernatant from the co-culture of *L. fermentum* + *L. plantarum* compared to the control. Additionally, the study was able to show that expression levels of genes linked to bacteriocin synthesis was significantly upregulated in the co-culture sample compared to the control (W. He et al., 2025). These results potentially suggest that for inhibition to be observed between the two LAB species in a well diffusion assay, incubation as a co-culture is needed before collecting the CFS. In summary, with the above-mentioned optimization to

5.3 Effects of fermentation on trypsin inhibitor activity in faba beans

One of the objectives of this project was to investigate the effect of fermentation on levels of trypsin inhibitors in faba beans. Results regarding the two LAB strains and *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 showed no reduction in TUI/mg unless they were in co-culture with *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. This stands partially in opposition to what has been shown in the literature, as all four microorganisms have been shown to reduce the content of trypsin inhibitors through fermentation (Adeyemo & Onilude, 2013; Barampama & Simard, 1994; Chi & Cho, 2016). The fermentations were, however, not conducted on faba beans, and with different strains, which could potentially explain why these differences are observed. Moreover, the lack of studies performing fermentation on faba beans with the intention of assessing the impact on trypsin inhibitor content/activity makes it hard to say if this project's observations are irregular. Nonetheless, specific strains of *L. plantarum* have been shown to reduce the trypsin inhibitor activity in faba bean-based products, with (Coda et al., 2015) showing that fermentation of doughs made of faba bean flour with *L. plantarum* VTT E-133328 resulted in a significant reduction compared to the control. However, again, this fermentation medium is different than what was utilized in this project.

Results showed that solid-state fermentation with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* reduced the TUI/mg significantly compared to the control, regardless of whether it was in a mono or co-culture setup. These results match the reductions seen (Qi et al., 2024), where they also performed solid-state fermentation, however, with *B. subtilis* L5 and the fermentation medium consisting of soybeans. Similarly, (Hwang et al., 2025) revealed that solid-state fermentation of soybean meal with *B. subtilis* MBLB2796 led to a degradation of trypsin inhibitor. These studies, combined with results obtained in this project, suggest that the reductive impact of solid-state fermentation with *B. subtilis* on trypsin inhibitors is replicated in faba beans and is not only applicable to soybeans.

The reduction in TUI/mg seen when fermenting with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* is likely caused by its strong proteolytic abilities. This can be exemplified by the findings in (Sharmila et al., 2018), where it was shown that a bacillopeptidase isolated from *B. subtilis* CFR5 displayed trypsin inhibitor degradation activity. Moreover, proteolysis as described previously is a key characteristic of natto fermentation (Rocchi et al., 2024), with studies like (Harwood & Kikuchi, 2022) showcasing that *B. subtilis* possesses a wide range of extracellular and intracellular proteases. Additionally, multiple studies have investigated the optimization and determining factors regarding these proteases (Degering et al., 2010; Nguyen & Nguyen, 2020).

The association with extracellular proteases was further shown to be applicable for the project's deployed strain: *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, as a bioinformatic approach showed the presence of several domains in the annotated genome being associated with protein families containing extracellular proteases. Furthermore, all the matches associated with the peptidase S8 protein family were annotated with protein names reported to be a part of the proteolytic system of *B. subtilis*, as described in (Harwood & Kikuchi, 2022).

A noticeable difference was observed between liquid fermentation and solid-state fermentation regarding fermentation with *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, as the microorganism in liquid fermentation did not reduce the TUI/mg significantly. This could potentially be explained by the sample's corresponding pH value, which was 6.6, indicating a neutral level, while pH values measured during solid-state fermentation with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* were at alkaline pH values around 8.2-8.5, which was significantly higher than the control. This difference in pH could potentially be important for the proteolytic activity, as the optimal pH for the bacillopeptidase found in

(Sharmila et al., 2018) regarding enzyme activity was shown to be pH 8.0. Therefore, the differences observed between the two fermentation media could potentially be caused by the pH not being optimal during liquid fermentation, and as a result, impact the microorganism's ability to degrade trypsin inhibitors.

Lastly, this is further supported by the fact that a major class of the extracellular proteases found in *B. subtilis* is classified as alkaline serine proteases (Harwood & Kikuchi, 2022). Results found during the bioinformatic screening of *B. subtilis* var. *natto* to search for protein families associated with extracellular proteases potentially further support this theory (see Figure 23). Seven Matches were found to be associated with the peptidase S8 protein family. All seven matches are classified as serine proteases in the literature. However, it is only serine protease Vpr, subtilisin AprE, cell wall-associated protease WpraA, minor protease Epr, and bacillopeptidase F, which are classified as extracellular proteases in the literature (Harwood & Kikuchi, 2022). In summary, these bioinformatics findings, together with experimental results, potentially suggest that TUI/mg reduction in faba beans with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* is pH dependent.

5.4 Changes to the VOC profile of faba beans through solid-state fermentation

The project also wanted to investigate if solid-state fermentation could impact the VOC profile of faba beans with a specific focus on the reduction of “beany” off-flavors. Therefore, GC-MS was performed, and the results revealed that unfermented faba beans are dominated by aldehydes. This is in agreement with the literature, as studies have shown that faba beans are dominated by aldehydes. This is exemplified by the findings in (Oomah et al., 2014), where 45 volatiles were identified in faba beans by GC-MS, with aldehydes being the primary compound class, making up 57% of total peak area. Furthermore, (Larsen et al., 2026) showed that in unfermented faba protein concentrate (FPC), aldehydes accounted for 61.9 of the total VOCs. These results are a bit lower than what was found during this project, with the aldehydes of unfermented soaked faba beans accounting for 71.2% of the VOC composition, but the trend of aldehydes being prominent remains.

After solid-state fermentation with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum*, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, the VOC profiles changed drastically. The shift in VOC profiles being dominated by aldehydes to generally ketones and alcohols dominating was also seen in (Larsen et al., 2026), where the VOC profiles of FPC after 24 h and 72 h fermentation with *L. fermentum* NSB2, *Lactiplantibacillus argetoratensis* (12-27B), *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, and *Bacillus velezensis* G17 were dominated by ketones and alcohols or either ketones or alcohols.

Another pattern seen was that solid-state fermentation with mono-cultures of *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 and *L. plantarum* 2-1 resulted in acids accounting for 7.5-10.2 %, which was a higher percentage compared to all other samples. This supports the previously discussed ability of LAB to produce organic acids and provides further support that acids are responsible for the significant decrease in pH observed for the samples fermented with LAB mono-cultures. Another strain-specific characteristic was seen for all samples containing *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. Here, the percentage of nitrogen-containing compounds (pyrazines, pyridines and pyrimidines) was increased. Furthermore, a PCA analysis showed that solid-state fermentation samples containing *B. subtilis* var. *natto* clustered in a placement corresponding to the placement of various N-compounds on the loading plot, suggesting that these compounds are significant for the VOC profiles of samples fermented with *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. This aligns with previous studies, where specifically the synthesis of pyrazines has been shown to be characteristic in natto fermentation, with (Kłosowski et al., 2021) showing that *B. subtilis* strains isolated from natto are capable of producing various alkylpyrazines. Moreover, (Rocchi et al., 2024) showed that the VOC profiles of chickpeas, green peas, red lentils, and lupins fermented with three different *B. subtilis* strains were largely comprised of various pyrazines. Lastly, the increase in pyrazines can be connected to and further supports the previously discussed high proteolytic activity seen in fermentations with *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. This is because pyrazines are known to be formed during the degradation of amino acids, which would be abundantly higher due to proteolysis (Fischer et al., 2022), or they can be produced directly by *B. subtilis* during solid-state fermentation, as shown in (Besson et al., 1997), where the formation of pyrazines was also linked to previously discussed ammonia.

The assessment of specific aldehydes associated with “beany” off flavor revealed that faba beans, which did not undergo microbial fermentation, contained a higher concentration of hexanal, pentanal, and 2-Octenal (E) compared to fermented samples. Furthermore, this pattern

was also seen in the PCA of VOC profiles, where loading plot positions of hexanal and pentanal corresponded to the control samples on the score plot. This is in agreement with the findings in (Larsen et al., 2026), where hexanal and pentanal were dominant in FPC samples before fermentation, with the concentration of hexanal being $> 1000 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, measurements in line with this project's. These findings are encouraging from an off-flavor perspective, as hexanal is a highly impactful compound concerning the “beany” VOC profile of legumes (see introduction).

Furthermore, the significant reduction in specifically the concentration of hexanal through solid-state fermentation regardless of the microorganism is in line with the current literature. It has been shown that strains of *L. fermentum*, *L. plantarum*, *S. cerevisiae*, and *B. subtilis* all could reduce the content of hexanal in different legume-based fermentation media (Fauconnier et al., 1999; Y. He et al., 2026; Meng et al., 2023; Schindler et al., 2011). These reductions of specifically hexanal and “beany” aldehydes in general could potentially be tied to the presence of the enzyme alcohol dehydrogenase (ADH) within the metabolism of the deployed microorganisms. This enzyme is of interest because, as described in the introduction, it converts aldehydes into alcohols (Fischer et al., 2022), and in (Nugroho et al., 2024) it was shown that isolated microbial ADH could specifically reduce hexanal and pentanal into hexanol and pentanol, respectively. Furthermore, the reduction in aldehydes and increase in alcohols specifically caused by the microorganism are supported by the observations seen regarding the shift in VOC profiles. The control samples were dominated by aldehydes at both 0 h and at 48 h, but most samples that underwent solid-state fermentation resulted in alcohols accounting for a higher percentage compared to the controls, supporting the potential theory that the presence of microorganisms causes enzymatic conversion of aldehydes.

Whether ADH is present within this project's specific strains is not known. However, as the different strains belong to species whose metabolism has been classified and studied, a potential indication can be had. Regarding *L. fermentum*, which is classified as an obligate heterofermentative (Zheng et al., 2020), it was shown in (Verce et al., 2020), which performed comparative genomics of 28 strains that ADH is present and conserved within the species core carbohydrate metabolism. Specifically, it can be found catalysing the conversion of acetyl-CoA into acetaldehyde and acetaldehyde into ethanol. With respect to *L. plantarum* (Tirwa et al., 2020) showed the presence of ADH in the genome of *L. plantarum* DMR17 in the mixed acid fermentation pathway. With respect to *S. cerevisiae*, alcohol dehydrogenase is part of the

fermentation pathway (Piškur et al., 2006), and the ADH utilized in (Nugroho et al., 2024) was isolated from *S. cerevisiae*. Lastly, for *B. subtilis* (Y. He et al., 2026) argued that the pattern of aldehydes being reduced to alcohol in natto fermentation was caused by ADH.

Another aldehyde associated with the “beany” off-flavor is benzaldehyde, which showed a different pattern compared to the other “beany” aldehydes. This was seen as in solid-state fermentation samples containing *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, the concentration was not significantly different from the controls; however, this pattern is also shown in the literature. (Y. Liu et al., 2018) identified benzaldehyde as a key aroma compound during natto fermentation. The reason why benzaldehyde is reduced in samples with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, and *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 compared to *B. subtilis* var. *natto* samples could potentially be linked to the strong proteolytic profile of *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. This is because benzaldehyde is primarily formed from the amino acid phenylalanine (Pripi-Nicolau et al., 2000), which potentially would be abundantly higher due to the amino acid being released under proteolytic activity by *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. In contrast, *L. fermentum* UFLA, *L. plantarum* 2-1, and *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 might not display the same level of proteolysis; however, they were seen to reduce the concentration of benzaldehyde significantly compared to the controls, as they might enzymatically be able to convert it to benzyl alcohol. Additionally, as mentioned in the introduction, the aldehyde 3-methyl-butanal is also primarily formed as a result of the degradation of amino acids released under proteolysis, and the normalized concentration of this compound after solid-state fermentation was significantly higher for three samples containing *B. subtilis* var. *natto* compared to the 0 h control. Here, the strong proteolytic abilities of *B. subtilis* could again, like with benzaldehyde, potentially be the explanation.

5.5 Using confocal microscopy to visualize the impact of fermentation on faba beans

The final objective of the project was to assess whether confocal microscopy could be used to visualize potential structural changes in faba beans following fermentation. Therefore, a preliminary methodology was tested. Images and staining of the soaked faba beans used as an uninoculated control (control 48 h) showed relative promise, displaying clearer structural definition and separation compared to other samples. Nevertheless, the interpretation of the

observed structures remains uncertain, as only these images showed this staining and quality pattern.

Comparing images of the soaked faba beans to similar images of faba beans obtained in previous studies enables potential identification/interpretation. The recent study (Fernandez Castaneda et al., 2026) used confocal laser microscopy to visualize the microstructure of soaked faba beans. The deployed methodology was similar to this project's, with one difference being that this study deployed fluorescein 5-isothiocyanate to target starch, but still used calcofluor white and Rhodamine B. Ultimately, the CLSM images from (Fernandez Castaneda et al., 2026) showed clearly defined cell walls visualised by the calcofluor white stain (blue signal). Furthermore, it was seen that with the blue cell wall surrounding each individual cell inside, many distributed circular/ball-shaped green structures were observed, which the study identified as starch. Lastly, in between and around the starch, red fluorescence was observed corresponding to the Rhodamine B stain (protein). With all this in mind, (Fernandez Castaneda et al., 2026) likely was able to visualize the structure and cellular components in the cotyledon of faba bean seeds, as the composition of a cell wall surrounding large starch granules with protein bodies in between matches the description of the microstructure of the cotyledon found in the literature (see figure 1) (Sharan et al., 2020).

When comparing the images of (Fernandez Castaneda et al., 2026) to the images obtained in this project, similarities can be seen, especially regarding the calcofluor white stain, as this project's images all showed well-defined cell-wall-like structures encompassing large oval/circular structures, as seen in (Fernandez Castaneda et al., 2026). This could indicate that the images of soaked faba beans obtained in this project may visualize individual cotyledon plant cells with cell walls and starch granules inside. Furthermore, similarities can be found between this project's images and the CLSM images in (Rovalino-Córdova et al., 2019), where calcofluor white also stained clearly defined cell-walls and Rhodamine B stained the protein bodies surrounding unstained dark spots, which the article identifies as starch granules. This further supports the notion that the oval/circular shapes seen in this project's images are starch granules, as this project methodology also didn't target starch with any stain, which would potentially result in them appearing as dark/black shapes, as seen in this project's images of soaked faba beans. In summary, on the basis of the images obtained from the soaked faba beans, when compared to similar results in the literature, it could be suggested that confocal

microscopy is an applicable method for visualizing different structures and cellular components in faba beans.

Regarding the images obtained from other samples, staining with the three selected dyes produced images that varied substantially in focus and fluorescence patterns, rendering direct comparison to the 48 h control difficult, as it could not be determined whether these differences were caused by fermentation impact, sample preparation, or microscopy settings. Consequently, for these images, a more comprehensive analysis was needed, which time constraints did not allow for.

The reason the images from these samples were different from images obtained from the 48 h control could be due to the sample preparation and staining process, as many of the images were unfocused. Therefore, in future work, another attempt with an optimised methodology is needed. Future attempts could include more technical replicates, as the conducted attempt was performed on one biological replicate with one technical replicate. This would help determine if what is seen on the images is representative of each sample. Furthermore, special attention should be given to the staining process and sample preparation. This might be especially true regarding Rhodamine B, as both (Rovalino-Córdova et al., 2019) and (Fernandez Castaneda et al., 2026) used a lower concentration of the stain compared to calcofluor white, which was not the case in this project's methodology, where all stains were used at the same concentration.

Nonetheless, it would be valuable to optimize the methodology, as it would be interesting to effectively visualise the structural impact of solid-state fermentation on faba beans. The visualization would be particularly informative for solid-state fermentation with *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, as the previously discussed highly proteolytic profile of the microorganism, coupled with the clear changes in texture observed after 48 h of fermentation (see Appendix 10), could potentially be seen in the microstructure of faba beans.

6. Conclusions

This master's thesis set out to further the understanding of microbial fermentation of faba beans by investigating four food-relevant strains, their interactions, and their impact on functional properties.

In conclusion, the strains are applicable in the fermentation of faba beans, as the performed fermentations revealed that *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, *L. plantarum* 2-1, *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625, and *B. subtilis* var. *natto* were able to grow in mono-cultures and co-cultures in both a liquid and a solid-state fermentation system. The only exception found was that *B. subtilis* var. *natto* was not detectable in co-culture with *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13, which may indicate inhibition. Furthermore, it can also be concluded that the pH of faba bean fermentation is strain-dependent, with mono-cultures of *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 and *L. plantarum* 2-1 significantly decreasing the pH in both fermentation systems, and samples with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* significantly raising the pH in solid-state fermentation.

Results from spot agar assays revealed further insights into the interactions between the four microorganisms, as it was shown that *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 and *L. plantarum* 2-1 could inhibit the growth of *B. subtilis* var. *natto*, with inhibition also appearing between strains of *L. fermentum* and *L. plantarum*.

The performed GC-MS and trypsin inhibitor assay revealed that four strains affect faba quality differently. Specifically, GC-MS showed that all strains, both as mono- and co-cultures, could shift the VOC profile of faba beans through solid-state fermentation and reduce the concentration of certain “beany” off-flavor compounds like hexanal. However, it was only solid-state fermentation with *B. subtilis* var. *natto* that led to a significant reduction in trypsin inhibitor activity, indicating that this strain is particularly useful for combating trypsin inhibitors in faba beans.

Lastly, a preliminary methodology using confocal microscopy showed promise in visualizing the different structures and components within the microstructure of faba beans. However, further testing and optimization were needed to conclude the effects of fermentation.

References

- Adamidou, S., Nengas, I., Grigorakis, K., Nikolopoulou, D., & Jauncey, K. (2011). Chemical composition and antinutritional factors of field peas (*Pisum sativum*), chickpeas (*Cicer arietinum*), and faba beans (*Vicia faba*) as affected by extrusion preconditioning and drying temperatures. *Cereal Chemistry*, 88(1), 80–86. <https://doi.org/10.1094/CCHEM-05-10-0077>
- Adeyemo, S. M., & Onilude, A. A. (2013). Enzymatic Reduction of Anti-nutritional Factors in Fermenting Soybeans by *Lactobacillus plantarum* Isolates from Fermenting Cereals. *Nigerian Food Journal*, 31(2), 84–90. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0189-7241\(15\)30080-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0189-7241(15)30080-1)
- Ako, K., Durand, D., Nicolai, T., & Becu, L. (2009). Quantitative analysis of confocal laser scanning microscopy images of heat-set globular protein gels. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 23(4), 1111–1119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODHYD.2008.09.003>
- Auchtung, J. M., Hallen-Adams, H. E., & Hutkins, R. (2025). Microbial interactions and ecology in fermented food ecosystems. *Nature Reviews Microbiology* 2025 23:10, 23(10), 622–634. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-025-01191-w>
- Avesani, S., Castiello, U., Ravazzolo, L., & Bonato, B. (2025). Volatile organic compounds in pea plants: a comprehensive review. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 16. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FPLS.2025.1591829>
- Avilés-Gaxiola, S., Chuck-Hernández, C., & Serna Saldívar, S. O. (2018). Inactivation Methods of Trypsin Inhibitor in Legumes: A Review. *Journal of Food Science*, 83(1), 17–29. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1750-3841.13985>
- Ayyash, M., Johnson, S. K., Liu, S. Q., Mesmari, N., Dahmani, S., Al Dhaheri, A. S., & Kizhakkayil, J. (2019). In vitro investigation of bioactivities of solid-state fermented lupin, quinoa and wheat using *Lactobacillus* spp. *Food Chemistry*, 275, 50–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2018.09.031>
- Bai, F. Y., Han, D. Y., Duan, S. F., & Wang, Q. M. (2022). The Ecology and Evolution of the Baker's Yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *Genes* 2022, Vol. 13, Page 230, 13(2), 230. <https://doi.org/10.3390/GENES13020230>
- Barampama, Z., & Simard, R. E. (1994). Oligosaccharides, Antinutritional Factors, and Protein Digestibility of Dry Beans as Affected by Processing. *Journal of Food Science*, 59(4), 833–838. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1365-2621.1994.TB08139.X>
- Besson, I., Creuly, C., Gros, J. B., & Larroche, C. (1997). Pyrazine production by *Bacillus subtilis* in solid-state fermentation on soybeans. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 47(5), 489–495. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S002530050961>
- Bohra, A., Tiwari, A., Kaur, P., Ganie, S. A., Raza, A., Roorkiwal, M., Mir, R. R., Fernie, A. R., Smýkal, P., & Varshney, R. K. (2022). The Key to the Future Lies in the Past: Insights from Grain Legume Domestication and Improvement Should Inform Future Breeding Strategies. *Plant & Cell Physiology*, 63(11), 1554–1572. <https://doi.org/10.1093/PCP/PCAC086>
- Bott, L., & Chambers IV, E. (2006). Sensory characteristics of combinations of chemicals potentially associated with beany aroma in foods. *Journal of Sensory Studies*, 21(3), 308–321. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1745-459X.2006.00067.X>
- Branda, S. S., González-Pastor, J. E., Ben-Yehuda, S., Losick, R., & Kolter, R. (2001). Fruiting body formation by *Bacillus subtilis*. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 98(20), 11621–11626. <https://doi.org/10.1073/PNAS.191384198>
- Buades Fuster, J. M., Sanchís Cortés, P., Perelló Bestard, J., & Grases Freixedas, F. (2017). Plant phosphates, phytate and pathological calcifications in chronic kidney disease.

- Nefrología (English Edition)*, 37(1), 20–28.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NEFROE.2017.01.018>
- Caplice, E., & Fitzgerald, G. F. (1999). Food fermentations: Role of microorganisms in food production and preservation. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 50(1–2), 131–149. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605\(99\)00082-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605(99)00082-3)
- Castro, M. P., Palavecino, N. Z., Herman, C., Garro, O. A., & Campos, C. A. (2011). Lactic acid bacteria isolated from artisanal dry sausages: Characterization of antibacterial compounds and study of the factors affecting bacteriocin production. *Meat Science*, 87(4), 321–329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MEATSCI.2010.11.006>
- Chang, J. Y., & Chang, H. C. (2011). Growth inhibition of foodborne pathogens by kimchi prepared with bacteriocin-producing starter culture. *Journal of Food Science*, 76(1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1750-3841.2010.01965.X>
- Cheng, Z., Yang, J., Yan, R., Wang, B., Bai, Y., Miao, Z., Sun, J., Li, H., Wang, X., & Sun, B. (2025). Interactive mechanism-guided microbial interaction dynamics in food fermentations: Lactic acid bacteria and yeasts as a case example. *Food Bioscience*, 68, 106453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FBIO.2025.106453>
- Chi, C. H., & Cho, S. J. (2016). Improvement of bioactivity of soybean meal by solid-state fermentation with *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* versus *Lactobacillus* spp. and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *LWT - Food Science and Technology*, 68, 619–625. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LWT.2015.12.002>
- Choi, S., Baek, M. gyung, Chung, M. J., Lim, S., & Yi, H. (2021). Distribution of bacteriocin genes in the lineages of *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*. *Scientific Reports 2021 11:1*, 11(1), 20063-. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-99683-1>
- Cichońska, P., & Ziarno, M. (2021). Legumes and Legume-Based Beverages Fermented with Lactic Acid Bacteria as a Potential Carrier of Probiotics and Prebiotics. *Microorganisms 2022, Vol. 10, Page 91, 10(1)*, 91. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MICROORGANISMS10010091>
- Coda, R., Melama, L., Rizzello, C. G., Curiel, J. A., Sibakov, J., Holopainen, U., Pulkkinen, M., & Sozer, N. (2015). Effect of air classification and fermentation by *Lactobacillus plantarum* VTT E-133328 on faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.) flour nutritional properties. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 193, 34–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJFOODMICRO.2014.10.012>
- Crépon, K., Marget, P., Peyronnet, C., Carrouée, B., Arese, P., & Duc, G. (2010). Nutritional value of faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.) seeds for feed and food. In *Field Crops Research* (Vol. 115, Number 3, pp. 329–339). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2009.09.016>
- De Deken, R. H. (1966). The Crabtree effect: a regulatory system in yeast. *Journal of General Microbiology*, 44(2), 149–156. <https://doi.org/10.1099/00221287-44-2-149>
- Degering, C., Eggert, T., Puls, M., Bongaerts, J., Evers, S., Maurer, K. H., & Jaeger, K. E. (2010). Optimization of protease secretion in *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus licheniformis* by screening of homologous and heterologous signal peptides. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 76(19), 6370–6376. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.01146-10>
- Delbes-Paus, C., Dorchies, G., Chaabna, Z., Callon, C., & Montel, M. C. (2010). Contribution of hydrogen peroxide to the inhibition of *Staphylococcus aureus* by *Lactococcus garvieae* in interaction with raw milk microbial community. *Food Microbiology*, 27(7), 924–932. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2010.05.031>
- Diez-Simon, C., Eichelsheim, C., Mumm, R., & Hall, R. D. (2020). Chemical and Sensory Characteristics of Soy Sauce: A Review. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 68(42), 11612. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ACS.JAFC.0C04274>

- Earl, A. M., Losick, R., & Kolter, R. (n.d.). *Ecology and genomics of Bacillus subtilis*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tim.2008.03.004>
- Eijsink, V. G. H., Axelsson, L., Diep, D. B., Håvarstein, L. S., Holo, H., & Nes, I. F. (2002). Production of class II bacteriocins by lactic acid bacteria; an example of biological warfare and communication. *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek*, *81*(1–4), 639–654.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1020582211262>
- Errington, J., & van der Aa, L. T. (2020). Microbe profile: *Bacillus subtilis*: Model organism for cellular development, and industrial workhorse. *Microbiology (United Kingdom)*, *166*(5), 425–427. <https://doi.org/10.1099/MIC.0.000922>
- Fauconnier, M. L., Mpambara, A., Delcarte, J., Jacques, P., Thonart, P., & Marlier, M. (1999). Conversion of green note aldehydes into alcohols by yeast alcohol dehydrogenase. *Biotechnology Letters*, *21*(7), 629–633.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1005593821577>
- Feng, Y., Liu, W., Mercadé-Prieto, R., & Chen, X. D. (2021). Dye-protein interactions between Rhodamine B and whey proteins that affect the photoproperties of the dye. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry*, *408*, 113092.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JPHOTOCHEM.2020.113092>
- Fernandez Castaneda, L. A., Kravchenko, O., Mátl, P., Lu, J., Tuccillo, F., Edelmann, M., Katina, K., Atas, M., Leong, S.-L. L., Langton, M., & Zamaratskaia, G. (2026). Compositional and microstructural changes in faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.) during soaking and boiling. *Current Research in Food Science*, *12*, 101383.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CRFS.2026.101383>
- Fijan, S. (2016). Antimicrobial Effect of Probiotics against Common Pathogens. *Probiotics and Prebiotics in Human Nutrition and Health*. <https://doi.org/10.5772/63141>
- Fischer, E., Cayot, N., & Cachon, R. (2022). Potential of Microorganisms to Decrease the “Beany” Off-Flavor: A Review. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, *70*(15), 4493–4508. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ACS.JAFC.1C07505>
- Gänzle, M. G. (2015). Lactic metabolism revisited: metabolism of lactic acid bacteria in food fermentations and food spoilage. *Current Opinion in Food Science*, *2*, 106–117.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COFS.2015.03.001>
- Gobbetti, M., & Corsetti, A. (1997). *Lactobacillus sanfrancisco* key sourdough lactic acid bacterium: a review. *Food Microbiology*, *14*(2), 175–187.
<https://doi.org/10.1006/FMIC.1996.0083>
- Hackmann, T. J. (2024). The vast landscape of carbohydrate fermentation in prokaryotes. *FEMS Microbiology Reviews*, *48*(4), fuae016.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/FEMSRE/FUAE016>
- Hackmann, T. J., & Zhang, B. (2023). The phenotype and genotype of fermentative prokaryotes. *Science Advances*, *9*(39), eadg8687.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/SCIADV.ADG8687>
- Hadfield, J., Croucher, N. J., Goater, R. J., Abudahab, K., Aanensen, D. M., & Harris, S. R. (2018). Phandango: an interactive viewer for bacterial population genomics. *Bioinformatics*, *34*(2), 292–293. <https://doi.org/10.1093/BIOINFORMATICS/BTX610>
- Harwood, C. R., & Kikuchi, Y. (2022). The ins and outs of *Bacillus* proteases: activities, functions and commercial significance. *FEMS Microbiology Reviews*, *46*(1), 1–20.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/FEMSRE/FUAB046>
- Hashem, C., Hochrinner, J., Bürgler, M. B., Rinnofner, C., Pichler, H., & Winkler, M. (2022). From linoleic acid to hexanal and hexanol by whole cell catalysis with a lipoxygenase, hydroperoxide lyase and reductase cascade in *Komagataella phaffii*. *Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences*, *9*, 965315.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/FMOLB.2022.965315>

- Hassaan, M. S., Soltan, M. A., & Abdel-Moez, A. M. (2015). Nutritive value of soybean meal after solid state fermentation with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* for Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus*. *Animal Feed Science and Technology*, *201*, 89–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ANIFEEDSCI.2015.01.007>
- He, W., Zeng, Y., Shen, J., Li, K., Zhou, Y., Zeng, X., & Pan, D. (2025). Enhanced bacteriocin production by lactic acid bacteria by co-culture of *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* and *Limosilactobacillus fermentum*. *Food Bioscience*, *68*, 106358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FBIO.2025.106358>
- He, Y., Jiang, Y., Li, D., Ou, X., Miao, X., Sun, M., Niu, H., Hua, M., Su, Y., Wang, J., & Liu, Z. (2026). Differences in Nutrition and Sensory Quality Between Cooked Soybeans, Fermented Natto, and Post-Ripening Natto. *Foods*, *15*(2), 237. <https://doi.org/10.3390/FOODS15020237>
- Henderson, H. M., Blank, G., & Sustackova, H. (1991). Thermal Inactivation of Pea Flour Lipoyxygenase. *Journal of Food Biochemistry*, *15*(2), 107–115. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1745-4514.1991.TB00148.X>
- Hsiao, C. P., & Siebert, K. J. (1999). Modeling the inhibitory effects of organic acids on bacteria. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, *47*(3), 189–201. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605\(99\)00012-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605(99)00012-4)
- Hwang, C. Y., Cho, E.-S., Lim, H. J., & Seo, M.-J. (2025). In vitro evaluation of *Bacillus subtilis* isolated from *Apis mellifera* for potential use as a probiotic feed additive in honeybees. *Scientific Reports 2025 16:1*, *16*(1), 3708-. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-33832-8>
- Jiang, X., Ding, H., Liu, Q., Wei, Y., Zhang, Y., Wang, Y., Lu, Y., Ma, A., Li, Z., & Hu, Y. (2020). Effects of peanut meal extracts fermented by *Bacillus natto* on the growth performance, learning and memory skills and gut microbiota modulation in mice. *The British Journal of Nutrition*, *123*(4), 383–393. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007114519002988>
- Kandler, O. (1983). Carbohydrate metabolism in lactic acid bacteria. *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek*, *49*(3), 209–224. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00399499>
- Kaur, M., Gray, C., & Barringer, S. (2025). Controlling Off-Odors in Plant Proteins Using Sequential Fermentation. *Foods*, *15*(1), 39. <https://doi.org/10.3390/FOODS15010039>
- Kerjean, J. R., Condon, S., Lodi, R., Kalantzopoulos, G., Chamba, J. F., Suomalainen, T., Cogan, T., & Moreau, D. (2000). Improving the quality of European hard-cheeses by controlling of interactions between lactic acid bacteria and propionibacteria. *Food Research International*, *33*(3–4), 281–287. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-9969\(00\)00048-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-9969(00)00048-X)
- Kiela, P. R., & Ghishan, F. K. (2016). Physiology of Intestinal Absorption and Secretion. *Best Practice & Research Clinical Gastroenterology*, *30*(2), 145–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BPG.2016.02.007>
- Kłósowski, G., Mikulski, D., & Pielech-Przybylska, K. (2021). Pyrazines Biosynthesis by *Bacillus* Strains Isolated from Natto Fermented Soybean. *Biomolecules 2021, Vol. 11, Page 1736*, *11*(11), 1736. <https://doi.org/10.3390/BIOM11111736>
- Larsen, N., Henriksen, M. G., Crocoll, C., Li, Q., Lametsch, R., Poojary, M. M., Krych, L., Petersen, M. A., & Jespersen, L. (2026). Enhancing the sensory and nutritional properties of faba bean protein through fermentation with lactic acid bacteria and *Bacillus* spp. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, *446*, 111549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJFOODMICRO.2025.111549>
- Leonard, W., Zhang, P., Ying, D., & Fang, Z. (2023). Surmounting the off-flavor challenge in plant-based foods. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, *63*(30), 10585–10606. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2022.2078275>

- Liu, M., Bayjanov, J. R., Renckens, B., Nauta, A., & Siezen, R. J. (2010). The proteolytic system of lactic acid bacteria revisited: a genomic comparison. *BMC Genomics*, *11*(1), 36. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2164-11-36>
- Liu, W., Tang, Y., Zhang, J., Bai, J., Zhu, Y., Zhu, L., Zhao, Y., Daglia, M., Xiao, X., & He, Y. (2025). Microbial Interactions in Food Fermentation: Interactions, Analysis Strategies, and Quality Enhancement. *Foods* *2025*, Vol. 14, Page 2515, *14*(14), 2515. <https://doi.org/10.3390/FOODS14142515>
- Liu, Y., Song, H. L., & Luo, H. (2018). Correlation between the key aroma compounds and gDNA copies of *Bacillus* during fermentation and maturation of natto. *Food Research International*, *112*, 175–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODRES.2018.06.033>
- Lobley, R. W., Franks, R., & Holmes, R. (1977). Subcellular Localization of Enterokinase in Human Duodenal Mucosa. *Clinical Science and Molecular Medicine*, *53*(6), 551–562. <https://doi.org/10.1042/CS0530551>
- Lumsden, C. L., Jägermeyr, J., Ziska, L., & Fanzo, J. (2024). Critical overview of the implications of a global protein transition in the face of climate change: Key unknowns and research imperatives. *One Earth*, *7*(7), 1187–1201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ONEEAR.2024.06.013>
- Luo, Z., Zhu, Y., Xiang, H., Wang, Z., Jiang, Z., Zhao, X., Sun, X., & Guo, Z. (2025). Advancements in Inactivation of Soybean Trypsin Inhibitors. *Foods*, *14*(6), 975. <https://doi.org/10.3390/FOODS14060975>
- Lv, Y. C., Song, H. L., Li, X., Wu, L., & Guo, S. T. (2011). Influence of Blanching and Grinding Process with Hot Water on Beany and Non-Beany Flavor in Soymilk. *Journal of Food Science*, *76*(1), S20–S25. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1750-3841.2010.01947.X>
- Malheiros, P. S., Sant'Anna, V., Todorov, S. D., & Franco, B. D. G. M. (2015). Optimization of growth and bacteriocin production by *Lactobacillus sakei* subsp. *sakei*2a. *Brazilian Journal of Microbiology*, *46*(3), 825. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1517-838246320140279>
- Man, L. L., & Xiang, D. J. (2023). Effect of LuxS/AI-2-mediated quorum sensing system on bacteriocin production of *Lactobacillus plantarum* NMD-17. *Folia Microbiologica* *2023* *68*:6, *68*(6), 855–866. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12223-023-01060-0>
- Mao, Y., Zhang, X., & Xu, Z. (2020). Identification of antibacterial substances of *Lactobacillus plantarum* DY-6 for bacteriostatic action. *Food Science and Nutrition*, *8*(6), 2854–2863. <https://doi.org/10.1002/FSN3.1585>
- Marco, M. L., Sanders, M. E., Gänzle, M., Arrieta, M. C., Cotter, P. D., De Vuyst, L., Hill, C., Holzapfel, W., Lebeer, S., Merenstein, D., Reid, G., Wolfe, B. E., & Hutkins, R. (2021). The International Scientific Association for Probiotics and Prebiotics (ISAPP) consensus statement on fermented foods. *Nature Reviews Gastroenterology & Hepatology* *2021* *18*:3, *18*(3), 196–208. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41575-020-00390-5>
- Mayer Labba, I. C., Frøkiær, H., & Sandberg, A. S. (2021). Nutritional and antinutritional composition of fava bean (*Vicia faba* L., var. *minor*) cultivars. *Food Research International*, *140*, 110038. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODRES.2020.110038>
- Meng, J., Wang, J. L., Hao, Y. P., Zhu, M. X., & Wang, J. (2023). Effects of *Lactobacillus fermentum* GD01 fermentation on the nutritional components and flavor substances of three kinds of bean milk. *LWT*, *184*, 115006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LWT.2023.115006>
- Nath, H., Samtiya, M., & Dhewa, T. (2022). Beneficial attributes and adverse effects of major plant-based foods anti-nutrients on health: A review. *Human Nutrition & Metabolism*, *28*, 200147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.HNM.2022.200147>
- NCYC 625 - *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* | National Collection of Yeast Cultures. (n.d.). Retrieved 17 May 2026, from <https://www.ncyc.co.uk/catalogue/saccharomyces-cerevisiae-var-diastaticus-625>

- Nguyen, T., & Nguyen, C. H. (2020). Determination of factors affecting the protease content generated in fermented soybean by *Bacillus subtilis* 1423. *Energy Reports*, 6, 831–836. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EGYR.2019.11.011>
- Nugroho, A. D. W., van Schalkwijk, S., Cebeci, S., Jacobs, S., Wesselink, W., Staring, G., Goerdalay, S., Prodan, A., Stijnman, A., Teuling, E., Broersen, K., & Bachmann, H. (2024). Biopurification using non-growing microorganisms to improve plant protein ingredients. *Npj Science of Food* 2024 8:1, 8(1), 48-. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41538-024-00290-x>
- Oomah, B. D., Razafindrainibe, M., & Drover, J. C. (2014). Headspace volatile components of Canadian grown low-tannin faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.) genotypes. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 94(3), 473–481. <https://doi.org/10.1002/JSFA.6272>
- Page, A. J., Cummins, C. A., Hunt, M., Wong, V. K., Reuter, S., Holden, M. T. G., Fookes, M., Falush, D., Keane, J. A., & Parkhill, J. (2015). Roary: rapid large-scale prokaryote pan genome analysis. *Bioinformatics*, 31(22), 3691–3693. <https://doi.org/10.1093/BIOINFORMATICS/BTV421>
- Papadimitriou, K., Alegría, Á., Bron, P. A., de Angelis, M., Gobbetti, M., Kleerebezem, M., Lemos, J. A., Linares, D. M., Ross, P., Stanton, C., Turrone, F., van Sinderen, D., Varmanen, P., Ventura, M., Zúñiga, M., Tsakalidou, E., & Kok, J. (2016). Stress Physiology of Lactic Acid Bacteria. *Microbiology and Molecular Biology Reviews*, 80(3), 837–890. <https://doi.org/10.1128/MMBR.00076-15>
- Parapouli, M., Vasileiadis, A., Afendra, A.-S., Hatziloukas, E., Parapouli, M., Vasileiadis, A., Afendra, A.-S., & Hatziloukas, E. (2020). *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and its industrial applications. *AIMS Microbiology* 2020 1:1, 6(1), 1–31. <https://doi.org/10.3934/MICROBIOL.2020001>
- Paysan-Lafosse, T., Andreeva, A., Blum, M., Chuguransky, S. R., Grego, T., Pinto, B. L., Salazar, G. A., Bileschi, M. L., Linares-López, F., Meng-Papaxanthos, L., Colwell, L. J., Grishin, N. V., Schaeffer, R. D., Clementel, D., Tosatto, S. C. E., Sonnhammer, E., Wood, V., & Bateman, A. (2025). The Pfam protein families database: embracing AI/ML. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 53(D1), D523–D534. <https://doi.org/10.1093/NAR/GKAE997>
- Pérez-Ramos, A., Madi-Moussa, D., Coucheney, F., & Drider, D. (2021). Current Knowledge of the Mode of Action and Immunity Mechanisms of LAB-Bacteriocins. *Microorganisms*, 9(10), 2107. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MICROORGANISMS9102107>
- Petroski, W., & Minich, D. M. (2020). Is There Such a Thing as “Anti-Nutrients”? A Narrative Review of Perceived Problematic Plant Compounds. *Nutrients* 2020, Vol. 12, Page 2929, 12(10), 2929. <https://doi.org/10.3390/NU12102929>
- Pfister, B., & Zeeman, S. C. (2016). Formation of starch in plant cells. *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences: CMLS*, 73(14), 2781. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S00018-016-2250-X>
- Piškur, J., Rozpedowska, E., Polakova, S., Merico, A., & Compagno, C. (2006). How did *Saccharomyces* evolve to become a good brewer? *Trends in Genetics*, 22(4), 183–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TIG.2006.02.002>
- Pradhananga, M. (2019). Effect of processing and soybean cultivar on natto quality using response surface methodology. *Food Science and Nutrition*, 7(1), 173–182. <https://doi.org/10.1002/FSN3.848>
- Pripi-Nicolau, L., De Revel, G., Bertrand, A., & Maujean, A. (2000). Formation of Flavor Components by the Reaction of Amino Acid and Carbonyl Compounds in Mild Conditions. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 48(9), 3761–3766. <https://doi.org/10.1021/JF991024W>

- Punia Bangar, S., Suri, S., Trif, M., & Ozogul, F. (2022). Organic acids production from lactic acid bacteria: A preservation approach. *Food Bioscience*, *46*, 101615. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FBIO.2022.101615>
- Qi, N., Zhan, X., Milmine, J., Chang, K.-H., & Li, J. (2024). A novel thermophilic strain of *Bacillus subtilis* with antimicrobial activity and its potential application in solid-state fermentation of soybean meal. *Microbiology Spectrum*, *12*(4). <https://doi.org/10.1128/SPECTRUM.02784-23>
- Queiroz, L. P., Nogueira, I. B. R., & Ribeiro, A. M. (2024). Flavor Engineering: A comprehensive review of biological foundations, AI integration, industrial development, and socio-cultural dynamics. *Food Research International*, *196*, 115100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODRES.2024.115100>
- Quintanilla-Casas, B., Bro, R., Løve Hinrich, J., & L. Davie-Martin, C. (2024). *Tutorial on PARADISE: PARAFAC2-based Deconvolution and Identification System for processing GC-MS data (version 6.1.x) v2*. <https://doi.org/10.17504/PROTOCOLS.IO.261GE5R3WG47/V2>
- Rasconi, S., Jobard, M., Jouve, L., & Sime-Ngando, T. (2009). Use of Calcofluor White for Detection, Identification, and Quantification of Phytoplanktonic Fungal Parasites. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, *75*(8), 2545. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.02211-08>
- Ricke, S. C. (2003). Perspectives on the use of organic acids and short chain fatty acids as antimicrobials. *Poultry Science*, *82*(4), 632–639. <https://doi.org/10.1093/PS/82.4.632>
- Ritter, S. W., Ensslin, S., Gastl, M. I., & Becker, T. M. (2024). Identification of key aroma compounds of faba beans (*Vicia faba*) and their development during germination – a SENSOMICS approach. *Food Chemistry*, *435*, 137610. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2023.137610>
- Rocchi, R., Zwinkels, J., Kooijman, M., Garre, A., & Smid, E. J. (2024). Development of novel natto using legumes produced in Europe. *Heliyon*, *10*(5), e26849. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.HELIYON.2024.E26849>
- Rosazza, T., Eigentler, L., Earl, C., Davidson, F. A., & Stanley-Wall, N. R. (2023). *Bacillus subtilis* extracellular protease production incurs a context-dependent cost. *Molecular Microbiology*, *120*(2), 105. <https://doi.org/10.1111/MMI.15110>
- Røssland, E., Borge, G. I. A., Langsrud, T., & Sørhaug, T. (2003). Inhibition of *Bacillus cereus* by strains of *Lactobacillus* and *Lactococcus* in milk. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, *89*(2–3), 205–212. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605\(03\)00149-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605(03)00149-1)
- Roalino-Córdova, A. M., Fogliano, V., & Capuano, E. (2019). The effect of cell wall encapsulation on macronutrients digestion: A case study in kidney beans. *Food Chemistry*, *286*, 557–566. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2019.02.057>
- Salim, R., Nehvi, I. B., Mir, R. A., Tyagi, A., Ali, S., & Bhat, O. M. (2023). A review on anti-nutritional factors: unraveling the natural gateways to human health. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, *10*, 1215873. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FNUT.2023.1215873>
- Sanger, M. J., & Danner, M. (2010). Aqueous Ammonia or Ammonium Hydroxide? Identifying a Base as Strong or Weak. *Journal of Chemical Education*, *87*(11), 1213–1216. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ED100536N>
- Schindler, S., Wittig, M., Zelena, K., Krings, U., Bez, J., Eisner, P., & Berger, R. G. (2011). Lactic fermentation to improve the aroma of protein extracts of sweet lupin (*Lupinus angustifolius*). *Food Chemistry*, *128*(2), 330–337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2011.03.024>
- Schwengers, O., Jelonek, L., Dieckmann, M. A., Beyvers, S., Blom, J., & Goesmann, A. (2021). Bakta: Rapid and standardized annotation of bacterial genomes via alignment-

- free sequence identification. *Microbial Genomics*, 7(11), 000685.
<https://doi.org/10.1099/MGEN.0.000685>
- Sharan, S., Zanghelini, G., Zotzel, J., Bonerz, D., Aschoff, J., Saint-Eve, A., & Maillard, M.-N. (2020). *COMPREHENSIVEREVIEWSINFOODSCIENCEANDFOODSAFETY* Fava bean (*Vicia faba* L.) for food applications: From seed to ingredient processing and its effect on functional properties, antinutritional factors, flavor, and <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12687>
- Sharmila, G. R., Halami, P. M., & Venkateswaran, G. (2018). Identification and characterization of a calcium dependent bacillopeptidase from *Bacillus subtilis* CFR5 with novel kunitz trypsin inhibitor degradation activity. *Food Research International*, 103, 263–272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODRES.2017.10.049>
- Shi, L., Mu, K., Arntfield, S. D., & Nickerson, M. T. (2017). Changes in levels of enzyme inhibitors during soaking and cooking for pulses available in Canada. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 54(4), 1014–1022. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S13197-017-2519-6>
- Siedler, S., Rau, M. H., Bidstrup, S., Vento, J. M., Aunsbjerg, S. D., Bosma, E. F., Mcnair, L. M., Beisel, C. L., & Neves, A. R. (2020). Competitive Exclusion Is a Major Bioprotective Mechanism of Lactobacilli against Fungal Spoilage in Fermented Milk Products. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 86(7).
<https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.02312-19>
- Skriver, E. V., Canoy, T. S., Sha, Y., Rasmussen, M. A., Khakimov, B., Knøchel, S., & Røder, H. L. (2026). Matrix matters: Context-driven metabolic shifts in *Bacillus cereus* and *Bacillus subtilis*. *Food Microbiology*, 138, 105066.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FM.2026.105066>
- Smit, B. A., Engels, W. J. M., & Smit, G. (2009). Branched chain aldehydes: production and breakdown pathways and relevance for flavour in foods. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 2008 81:6, 81(6), 987–999. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S00253-008-1758-X>
- Stubbendieck, R. M., & Straight, P. D. (2016). Multifaceted Interfaces of Bacterial Competition. *Journal of Bacteriology*, 198(16), 2145–2155.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/JB.00275-16>
- Tao, A., Zhang, H., Duan, J., Xiao, Y., Liu, Y., Li, J., Huang, J., Zhong, T., & Yu, X. (2022). Mechanism and application of fermentation to remove beany flavor from plant-based meat analogs: A mini review. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 13, 1070773.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/FMICB.2022.1070773>
- Tayade, R., Kulkarni, K. P., Jo, H., Song, J. T., & Lee, J. D. (2019). Insight Into the Prospects for the Improvement of Seed Starch in Legume—A Review. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 10, 459939. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FPLS.2019.01213>
- Tirwa, R. K., Najar, I. N., Thakur, N., Chaurasia, L. K., & Tamang, B. (2020). Draft genome sequence of *Lactobacillus plantarum* strain DMR17 isolated from homemade cow dahi of Sikkim Himalayan region: an evaluation of lactate fermentation and secondary metabolism. *Archives of Microbiology* 2020 203:1, 203(1), 305–315.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/S00203-020-02023-6>
- Verce, M., De Vuyst, L., & Weckx, S. (2020). Comparative genomics of *Lactobacillus fermentum* suggests a free-living lifestyle of this lactic acid bacterial species. *Food Microbiology*, 89, 103448. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FM.2020.103448>
- Verni, M., Wang, C., Montemurro, M., De Angelis, M., Katina, K., Rizzello, C. G., & Coda, R. (2017). Exploring the Microbiota of Faba Bean: Functional Characterization of Lactic Acid Bacteria. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 8(DEC), 2461.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/FMICB.2017.02461>

- Wang, C., Chen, J., Tian, W., Han, Y., Xu, X., Ren, T., Tian, C., & Chen, C. (2023). Natto: A medicinal and edible food with health function. *Chinese Herbal Medicines*, 15(3), 349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHMED.2023.02.005>
- Wei, Q., Wolf-Hall, C., & Chang, K. C. (2001). Natto characteristics as affected by steaming time, Bacillus strain, and fermentation time. *Journal of Food Science*, 66(1), 167–173. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1365-2621.2001.TB15601.X>
- Wu, G. (2009). Amino acids: metabolism, functions, and nutrition. *Amino Acids* 2009 37:1, 37(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S00726-009-0269-0>
- Xu, J., Wang, Z., Shi, Z., Liu, M., Fan, X., Zhang, T., Wu, Z., Zhu, M., Tu, M., & Pan, D. (2025). Detection and development of lactic acid bacteria bacteriocins - A hint on the screening of bacteriocins of lactic acid bacteria. *LWT*, 222, 117627. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LWT.2025.117627>
- Yang, Y., Tao, W. Y., Liu, Y. J., & Zhu, F. (2008). Inhibition of *Bacillus cereus* by lactic acid bacteria starter cultures in rice fermentation. *Food Control*, 19(2), 159–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCONT.2007.03.002>
- Zheng, J., Wittouck, S., Salvetti, E., Franz, C. M. A. P., Harris, H. M. B., Mattarelli, P., O'toole, P. W., Pot, B., Vandamme, P., Walter, J., Watanabe, K., Wuyts, S., Felis, G. E., Gänzle, M. G., & Lebeer, S. (2020). A taxonomic note on the genus *Lactobacillus*: Description of 23 novel genera, emended description of the genus *Lactobacillus* beijerinck 1901, and union of *Lactobacillaceae* and *Leuconostocaceae*. *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology*, 70(4), 2782–2858. <https://doi.org/10.1099/IJSEM.0.004107>
- Zhou, N., Swamy, K. B. S., Leu, J. Y., McDonald, M. J., Galafassi, S., Compagno, C., & Piškur, J. (2017). Coevolution with bacteria drives the evolution of aerobic fermentation in *Lachancea kluyveri*. *PLOS ONE*, 12(3), e0173318. <https://doi.org/10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0173318>
- Zhu, J., Tan, N. K., Kikuchi, K., Kaur, A., & New, E. J. (2024). BODIPY-based Fluorescent Indicators for Lipid Droplets. *Analysis and Sensing*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1002/ANSE.202300049>

Appendix

Pictures from agar spot assay

L. fermentum UFLA CH-13 vs *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625

L. plantarum 2-1 vs *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625

Appendix 1: Results of spot agar assay between *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 (left) and *L. plantarum* 2-1 (right) as producers vs *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 as indicator (lawn). Pictures are examples from triplicates. Small black dots indicate the position of the negative control.

S. cerevisiae NCYC 625 vs *L. plantarum* 2-1

S. cerevisiae NCYC 625 vs *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13

Appendix 2: Results of spot agar assay between *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 as producer vs *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 (right) and *L. plantarum* 2-1 (left) as indicators (lawn). Pictures are examples from triplicates. Small black dots indicate the position of the negative control.

B. subtilis var. *natto* vs *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625

S. cerevisiae NCYC 625 vs *B. subtilis* var. *natto*

Appendix 3: Results of spot agar assay between *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 and *B. subtilis* var. *natto*. Left: *B. subtilis* var. *natto* as producer vs *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 as indicator. Right: *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 as producers vs *B. subtilis* var. *natto* as indicator (lawn). Pictures are examples from triplicates. Small black dots indicate the position of the negative control.

LAB vs LAB spot agar assay:

Appendix 4: Results from agar spot assay testing multiple *L. fermentum* strains against multiple *L. plantarum* strains. The names before “vs” act as a producer (spot) while the name after acts as an indicator (lawn). Three technical replicates of producer strains are shown on the plates, while pictures are examples from triplicates. Small dots indicate the position of the negative control. No inhibition was noted if: < 0.1 cm between colony outline and lawn.

Images from confocal microscopy

For all pictures below:

A: Stained with BODIPY

B: Stained with Rhodamine B

C: No stain

D: stained with Calcofluor White

100 μm scale bar

0 h control:

Appendix 5: Confocal microscopy images of 0 h control samples from solid-state fermentation. Letters indicate the different staining conditions. A: BODIPY; B: Rhodamine B; C: No stain; D: Calcofluor white. Images include a scale bar of 100 μm , providing spatial reference for observed plant cell structures.

L. fermentum UFLA CH-13:

Appendix 6: Confocal microscopy images of *L. fermentum* UFLA CH-13 (48 h) samples from solid-state fermentation. Letters indicate the different staining conditions. A: BODIPY; B: Rhodamine B; C: No stain; D: Calcofluor white

L. plantarum 2-1:

Appendix 7: Confocal microscopy images of *L. plantarum* 2-1 (48 h) samples from solid-state fermentation. Letters indicate the different staining conditions. A: BODIPY; B: Rhodamine B; C: No stain; D: Calcofluor white.

S. cerevisiae NCYC 625:

Appendix 8: Confocal microscopy images of *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 (48 h) samples from solid-state fermentation. Letters indicate the different staining conditions. A: BODIPY; B: Rhodamine B; C: No stain; D: Calcofluor white

B. Subtilis var. *natto*:

Appendix 9: Confocal microscopy images of *B. subtilis* var. *natto* (48 h) samples from solid-state fermentation. Letters indicate the different staining conditions. A: BODIPY; B: Rhodamine B; C: No stain; D: Calcofluor white

Pictures of faba beans before and after solid-state fermentation:

Appendix 10: Left: Soaked faba beans prior to solid-state fermentation (0 h). Right: Faba beans after 48 h solid-state fermentation with *B. subtilis* var. *natto*

Declaration of using generative AI tools (for students)

I/we have used generative AI as an aid/tool (please tick)

I/we have **NOT** used generative AI as an aid/tool (please tick)

If generative AI is permitted in the exam, but you haven't used it in your exam paper, you just need to tick the box stating that you have not used GAI. You don't have to fill in the rest.

List which GAI tools you have used and include the link to the platform (if possible):

ChatGPT, <https://chatgpt.com/>

Grammarly, <https://www.grammarly.com/>

Describe how generative AI has been used in the exam paper:

1) Purpose (what did you use the tool for?)

When revising a text I had written myself I used generative AI to proofread and improve grammar and spelling. This was done by making the AI point out mistakes and errors, like spelling and punctuation errors.

If I was uncertain about ideas I had AI help with clarifications. This could be regarding overall structure or concepts.

Help with the technical support and refinement regarding coding for R studio.

2) Work phase (when in the process did you use GAI?)

Majority of the usage was during final revision when a text needed proofreading.

3) What did you do with the output? (including any editing of or continued work on the output)

Suggestions made by the AI were critically evaluated one by one before deciding whether to manually implement them.

Please note: Content generated by GAI that is used as a source in the paper requires correct use of quotation marks and source referencing. [Read the guidelines from Copenhagen University Library at KUnet.](#)